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Using Conceptors to Extract Abstraction Hierarchies from Corpora of Natural Text

Combatting Word Polysemy Using Word Sense Disambiguation Techniques

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Abstract

This thesis documents a project wherein a method was developed for extracting hierarchies of abstraction between concepts from large unlabeled corpora of text. To this end conceptors were employed, which is a mechanism for neurosymbolic organisation and which includes a measure for estimating concept-to-concept abstraction, based on the Löwner order.

Previous research has focused on using conceptors of word embeddings to estimate word-to-word abstraction, but this fails to consider polysemy: the property that words can have multiple senses. One of the main contributions of this thesis is therefore to move from word-to-word abstraction to sense-to-sense abstraction instead, by incorporating findings from the current state of the art in the linguistical problem of computational word sense disambiguation. Secondly, a graded extension of the available two-valued measure of conceptor abstraction was developed, to enable a finer-grained insight in abstraction values. These two points were integrated into a single abstraction hierarchy distillation pipeline, on which initial experiments were conducted using the BookCorpus.

Results have shown that conceptors are suitable for estimating abstraction relations between word senses, but for the present experiment need a considerable amount of exemplar occurrences before the abstraction estimation becomes accurate. Additionally, the word sense classification step seems to work, but this cannot be quantified in the current experiments due to a lack of quantitative accuracy measures on unlabeled data. However, manual inspection has resulted in several points upon which this step can be improved, including the detection of open compounds, metaphors and named entities. Finally, the movement towards abstraction at sense-level from word-level has opened discussions in how formal definitions of abstraction might not align with human abstraction interpretation in the context of discourse.

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PART I

INTRODUCTION

1 Introduction

1.1 Concepts, Polysemy, Abstraction

Humans learn their first language primarily through observation and recitation: we observe our parents talk and try to mimic their language use [28]. Through this relatively simple practice we can eventually derive a plethora of semantic relations between words: “nice” means the same as “good”; “good” is the opposite of “bad”; and a “brim” is part of “hat”. Another semantic intuition that we build up over time is the relation of abstraction: “animal” is more abstract than “human”, whereas “human” is more abstract than “woman”. All such relations are organised together into empirical lexical–semantic networks [76].

The abstraction relation as defined above is modelled by word *hyponymy*, which connects an abstract “blanket” term or supertype with a more concrete subtype that falls under the blanket term. For example, “human” is a hyponym of “animal”, as “human” is a subtype of the supertype “animal” – a human is *a kind of* animal. The formal analog of hyponymy is the set-theoretic logical *subsumption* model, where class X subsumes class Y if and only if all things that are part of X are also part of Y , formally $X \supseteq Y$. Such formal abstraction relations together form an *ontology*: a hierarchical taxonomy of categories of concepts, structured as a tree where the topmost category (the root) represents the most *general* concept, and concepts become increasingly *specialised* as we move down the tree towards the leaves. An example for an upper ontology, i.e. an ontology that starts at the globally most abstract term “anything” and works its way down from there, is listed in Figure 1.1.

This thesis focuses specifically on word-to-word abstraction relations, and attempts to shed a light on whether the human notion of abstraction aligns with the formal hyponymy or subsumption model as it is defined above. They do not necessarily align due to the fact that the human lexical–semantic network acquisition is empirical: this implies that there is no necessity for an underlying symbolic model on which the network is funded.

We explore a method of extracting a human word abstraction hierarchy from a large corpus of unlabeled natural text. The method is adapted from the pipeline that is proposed in Bricman [5], who uses conceptors of contextual word embeddings to represent words and inter-word abstraction relations. A contextual word embedding (CWE) is a vector embedding that represents a word as it is used in the context of a sentence. They are commonly extracted from (large) language transformer models such as GPT (Generative Pre-Training) [61], ELMo (Embeddings from Language Models) [60] or BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [11]. A conceptor can be seen as an ellipsoid “envelope” of a cloud of such embeddings, thereby providing a geometric characterisation of a set of word exemplars. An important detail of conceptors is that it has a measure of inter-conceptor abstraction, making conceptors especially suitable for the task at hand when conceptors are created from an embedding cloud on a word-by-word basis. Figure 1.2 shows an example of how sentences of natural text are converted into conceptors representing words.

A problem that emerged from the work of Bricman [5] is that of *polysemy*, that is the property that words can have multiple meanings, or *senses*. Take as example the word “plant”, which

Figure 1.1. Example of an upper ontology. Source: Russell, Norvig, and Davis [65, figure 12.1].

Figure 1.2. Natural sentences (*left*) are converted to contextual word embeddings (*mid*), i.e. high-dimensional embedding vectors. These are then combined into conceptor “envelopes” (*right*) on a word-by-word basis, which can directly be compared in terms of abstraction.

Figure 1.3. A two-dimensional UMAP [46] projection of BERT embeddings from natural sentences using three senses of the noun “bow”. The used sentences originate from the CoarseWSD-20 corpus [42], which is covered further in Section 3.3.

can be used to refer to immobile organisms from the family of *plantae*, but it can also be used to refer to an industrial factory. Moreover, it could be used as a verb to refer to the action of sticking plants into the soil.

The sentential context of a word changes in accordance with its sense [49] — in terms of parts-of-speech (e.g. is the word a noun or a verb), but also in terms of semantic context (e.g. the “factory” sense of “plant” will rarely be used in the semantic context of botany). This variance in context is reflected in the geometry of the contextual word embeddings [14]: for example, BERT places embeddings of a word’s different senses into distinct “sense regions” in the embedding space [75].

An example of this phenomenon can be found in Figure 1.3. Here, a two-dimensional UMAP [46] projection is shown from BERT embeddings of sentences that use one of three possible senses for the word “bow”: the bow of a ship; the bow of a bow and arrow; and the bow of a violin. Here can be seen that almost all embeddings for bow#ship are very well-separated from the other embeddings in both UMAP dimensions. The embeddings from bow#arrow and bow#violin are separated in the y -dimension, but are in line with each other on the x -dimension.

If word polysemy is not accounted for in the distillation process of word-to-word abstraction hierarchies, the embeddings of all of a word’s senses are lumped together to form a single vector cloud and are together aggregated into a singular conceptor. This conceptor is now tasked with describing multiple word meanings at once, which means that it loses its expressivity: it might need to represent concepts of different abstraction levels at the same time. Instead, aggregation of word embeddings into conceptors should occur at the *lemma*-level, where a lemma is defined as a word pertaining to a single word sense. The previously covered bow#ship, bow#arrow and bow#violin are in therefore lemmas, and for our example word “plant”, all three of the given senses have their own lemma (sc. plant#organism, plant#factory, plant#bury, respectively).

Aggregation at the lemma-level entails that a *word sense disambiguation* step needs to be introduced. The process of word sense disambiguation (WSD) identifies the sense of a word as it is used in a sentence, which means that it has the power to lemmatise CWEs. It is one of the oldest problems in computational linguistics, and was formulated as early as 1949 [73]. It has seen regular attention throughout the years [55], and recently developed solutions have become quite accurate with the advent of deep learning and explosion of available computational resources. This thesis therefore focuses on the implementation of a WSD system in a method for abstraction hierarchy extraction.

A core goal of this thesis is to shed a light on the extent with which a computationally extracted abstraction hierarchy aligns with both the formal definition of logical subsumption and intuitive human estimations of abstraction. An explicit property of logical subsumption is that the relationship is *transitive*, i.e. if A subsumes B and B subsumes C , then A also subsumes C . This is a concrete criterion on which we can test the abstraction extraction method. This leads us to the research questions that this thesis attempts to answer:

Research Question. Can the abstraction hierarchy between word lemmata be recovered using conceptors of contextual embedding clouds? What are the difficulties?

- i. How can clouds of polysemous word embeddings be split into clouds of monosemous lemmata?
 - a. How can recent developments in the linguistic problem of word sense disambiguation be used to achieve this?
- ii. How can conceptors be used to estimate the abstraction relation between two conceptors?
- iii. How can these binary abstraction relations be aggregated into hierarchies of abstractions?
- iv. To what extent do the estimated abstraction hierarchies correspond with both the formally defined subsumption model and intuitive human estimations for abstraction hierarchies?
 - a. Is the abstraction relation transitive?

A Note on Notation

Throughout this thesis, a distinction must be made between the meaning of a word and *the word itself*; for example, with “tree” can be meant a tall plant with a trunk and branches and leaves, or a word that is made up of two vowels and two syllables and that rhymes with “vee”. This distinction is made by using a separate font for the latter: if a word is typed with a sans font, then it is meant to denote the word itself rather than (one of) the meaning(s) that the word can refer to.

1.2 *Outline*

The remainder of this thesis is subdivided in three parts. Part II provides a theoretical framework that forms the basis for the contributions of this thesis. This framework revolves around the two most significant components for the present subject: Chapter 2 covers the mechanism of conceptors, and Chapter 3 goes over the state of the art of the linguistic problem of word sense disambiguation. Part III focuses on the concrete implementational and experimental contributions of this thesis, which are used to answer the research questions posed above. Chapter 4 introduces the developed pipeline for abstraction hierarchy extraction, and Chapter 5

explains the operational details for the experiments that were conducted with this pipeline. Finally, Part IV presents and interprets the results of these experiments. Chapter 6 presents the experimental results, and Chapter 7 interprets them and attempts to put the results into broader context. Chapter 8 concludes by answering the research questions concretely and provides an outlook for future research.

PART II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2 Conceptors

This chapter introduces the mechanism of *conceptors*, a matrix construct with properties that allow for neurosymbolic organisation and reasoning. This mechanism forms the basis and first motivation for pursuing the research questions that are posed in this thesis.

Section 2.1 provides an introduction to conceptors, leading to a formal definition and core properties. Section 2.2 covers the theory behind the abstraction ordering that is defined for conceptors. Finally, Section 2.3 gives a short overview of other conceptor application domains.

2.1 Introducing Conceptors

The conceptor was introduced by Jaeger [25] as a way to control recurrent neural networks (RNNs). A conceptor is able to characterise an input pattern that drives an RNN, based on the geometry of the network’s internal neural state. This characterisation can then be used to let the network auto-regenerate the driving pattern, by applying the conceptor as a filter on the network’s internal states. An introduction to conceptors can be found in Jaeger [24].

In general, a conceptor can be used to describe the geometry of any (multidimensional) point cloud. Let us consider a finite sequence of length L of N -dimensional data points $(x_k)_{k=1}^L$, where $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^N$. This sequence can be concatenated into an $N \times L$ matrix X , the geometry of which can now be described using a conceptor.

Let us define the state correlation matrix of X as $R = \frac{1}{L}XX^\top$, which can be interpreted geometrically as representing an N -dimensional ellipsoid that provides an initial characterisation of the geometry of X : the ellipsoid’s principal axes point in the directions along which the points in X vary most, and their lengths are defined by R ’s singular values $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_N$. Figure 2.1a shows the conversion from an example sequence to a correlation matrix ellipsoid.

A conceptor is essentially a derivative from this correlation matrix, with all its singular values scaled so that they range in $[0, 1]$. This implies that the conceptor ellipsoid falls entirely within the unit spheroid. The conceptor’s singular values can be defined in terms of the correlation matrix’s singular values as: $s_i = \sigma_i / (\sigma_i + \alpha^{-2})$. Here, α is a design parameter called *aperture*. With this scaling equation in mind, we can define a conceptor matrix in terms of a correlation matrix and an aperture value:

$$C = C(R, \alpha) = R(R + \alpha^{-2}I)^{-1}, \quad (2.1)$$

where I corresponds to the $N \times N$ identity matrix. Figure 2.1b shows how the conceptor ellipsoid as compared to the correlation matrix ellipsoid. Conform Jaeger [25, definition 2], we define C_N as the set of all conceptors of order N . It is defined as follows:

Definition 1. *A conceptor matrix is a positive semidefinite matrix whose singular values range in $[0, 1]$. We denote the set of all $N \times N$ conceptor matrices by C_N .*

The aperture parameter α of a conceptor determines how “opened up” the conceptor ellipsoid becomes. The smaller the aperture, the smaller the conceptor’s singular values, and the larger

(a) Going from a cloud of data points to a correlation matrix. The gray data points have a correlation matrix that is represented by the black dashed ellipse.

(b) Going from a correlation matrix to a conceptor. Figure 2.1a's correlation matrix is represented by the black dashed ellipse, and the resulting conceptor ($\alpha = 1$) by the black ellipse.

(c) Conceptors with 15 aperture values linearly spaced between 0.1 (innermost ellipse) and 5 (outermost ellipse). The conceptor from Figure 2.1b, with $\alpha = 1$, has a dashed ellipse.

Figure 2.1. Correlation matrices, conceptors, and aperture values for a two-dimensional data sequence.

the aperture, the more they approach one. Figure 2.1c shows how the aperture parameter affects a two-dimensional conceptor ellipse.

A conceptor matrix, as it defined above, can be used to control an RNN by “projecting” its internal state values to the “subspace” that is characteristic for the pattern represented by the conceptor. The quotation marks are necessary here since a driving pattern is not necessarily confined to a proper linear subspace $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathbb{R}^N$, and the corresponding conceptor is as such not necessarily a proper projector matrix. Instead, in the conceptor ellipsoid's principal axis directions for which the axes' lengths fall in $(0, 1)$, the network states will be *dampened* (where the degree of dampening is adjusted by the aperture parameter). Therefore, the conceptor matrix can be seen as a directional dampening of internal RNN state values to fall within the geometric bound defined by the conceptor matrix' ellipsoid, which in turn is defined by the ellipsoid's principal axes and orientation.

Boolean Operators on Conceptors

A special feature of conceptors is that they can be combined using operations that share many properties with Boolean operators, which motivates naming them AND, OR and NOT (\vee , \wedge , \neg). Speaking in terms of controlling operation modes of RNNs, where being under control of a conceptor C entails only allowing internal neural state values within the geometric bound that is defined by C , we can intuitively describe these operations as follows:

- AND** Being under control of $C_1 \vee C_2$ entails only allowing internal state values that fall within the geometric bound of both C_1 and C_2 ;
- OR** Being under control of $C_1 \wedge C_2$ entails allowing internal state values that fall within the geometric bound of either C_1 or C_2 ;

(a) The conjunction of two conceptors: $C_1 \wedge C_2$. (b) The disjunction of two conceptors: $C_1 \vee C_2$. (c) The negation of a conceptor: $\neg C$.

Figure 2.2. Boolean operations on order-2 conceptors. For all figures, the grey ellipse represents the operand(s), and the black ellipse the result. The dotted circle is the unit circle.

NOT Being under control of $\neg C$ entails allowing internal state values that fall within a geometric bound that is orthogonal with C .

Figure 2.2 shows how these Boolean operations impact conceptor ellipses. Conform Sections 3.9.2 and 3.9.3 of Jaeger [25], the formal definitions of these operations are as follows:

Definition 2. For any two conceptors $C_1, C_2 \in C_N$ ($N \in \mathbb{N}$), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \neg C_1 &:= I - C_1; \\ C_1 \wedge C_2 &:= (\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{R}(C_1) \cap \mathcal{R}(C_2)}(C_1^\dagger + C_2^\dagger - I)\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{R}(C_1) \cap \mathcal{R}(C_2)})^\dagger; \\ C_1 \vee C_2 &:= \neg(\neg C_1 \wedge \neg C_2), \end{aligned}$$

where: I is the $N \times N$ identity matrix; $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{R}(C_1) \cap \mathcal{R}(C_2)}$ is the projector matrix on $\mathcal{R}(C_1) \cap \mathcal{R}(C_2)$; $\mathcal{R}(M)$ the range, or column space, of any matrix M ; and M^\dagger is the pseudoinverse, or Moore–Penrose inverse, of M .

The existence of Boolean operators for conceptors naturally leads to the development of a complete propositional logic for conceptors. It turns out that almost all laws of propositional logic carry over to the conceptor operators, with the exception of the absorption rules and the laws of distributivity.

2.2 Conceptor Abstraction

The existence of an abstraction relation between conceptors is the primary motivation behind this thesis. It revolves around the Löwner order [43], which is a partial order \leq that is defined by the convex cone of positive semi-definite matrices. The formal definition is as follows:

Definition 3 (Löwner order). For any two Hermitian matrices A and B of order N , we have that $A \leq B$ if and only if $A - B$ is positive semidefinite.

Figure 2.3. Different scenarios with two conceptors A and B , and their Löwner ordering.

Since conceptors are positive semidefinite, we find that C_N is a subset of the domain of \leq . Figure 2.3 shows examples of conceptors and their Löwner ordering, which might give an intuition about how the Löwner order on the class of conceptors, that is the order (C_N, \leq) , can be interpreted as an order of abstraction. Jaeger [25, propositions 13 and 14] proved this formally, by proving (i.a.) the following equivalence:

Theorem 1. *Let C_N be the set of $N \times N$ conceptors. Then for arbitrary $A, B \in C_N$, we have that $A \leq B$ if and only if there exists a $C \in C_N$ such that $A = B \wedge C$.*

Put in words, conceptor A is less abstract or more concrete than conceptor B if and only if you need to conjugate B with another conceptor C to get A . Note though that $0_{N \times N}$ is a conceptor as well, and $B \vee 0_{N \times N} = B$, confirming the reflexivity of \leq .

Conceptor Abstraction for Words Clouds

Bricman [5] made the first steps towards using this abstraction relation to estimate word-to-word abstraction using conceptors of contextual word vector clouds. The problem with the Löwner order is that it is categorical, viz. we have either $A \leq B$ or $A \not\leq B$. However, the real-wor(l)d data that was used was too noisy for such a strict definition to be insightful. This is the reason that a relaxation of the Löwner order was used for mapping abstraction relations. This was done by estimating the extent with which the conceptor difference matrix is positive semidefinite, which is equivalent to having only nonnegative eigenvalues. The average eigenvalue magnitude of the difference matrix of two conceptors was therefore used to estimate these conceptors' abstraction relation. The formal specification of this measure is given in Section 4.

2.3 Other Application Domains

As described in the previous sections, conceptors were primarily developed to control RNNs in the task of pattern recreation, where multiple patterns can be stored in and recreated by a single RNN [26]. There are however a multitude of other application domains for conceptors, many of which are mentioned in the introductory report [25]. Some examples are:

Diagonal conceptors Conceptors are square $N \times N$ matrices, which implies that linear operations on conceptors, such as applying it as a directional dampener on an RNN state, have a computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$. In the context of conceptor-aided RNNs, N is equal to the total number of neurons, making conceptors not very scalable. De Jong [10] introduces *diagonal* conceptors, reducing computational complexity to $\mathcal{O}(N)$, and which achieve identical accuracy as regular conceptors on elementary benchmark tests. However, a slight decrease in stability of the auto-regeneration of learned patterns was observed.

Fuzzy conceptor logic The Boolean operations that are defined in the preceding sections are inherently two-valued. Mossakowski, Diaconescu, and Glauer [53] argue however that conceptors are naturally fuzzy, and have therefore made the first steps towards developing a fuzzy conceptor logic.

Continual learning In He and Jaeger [21], conceptors were used in a modified back propagation algorithm to prevent *catastrophic inferencing* [45] and thereby enabling continual learning. This has been later used for example in the context of sentence encoding [40].

Sound synthesis Kiefer [29] used conceptor-controlled RNNs in the field of sound synthesis, where conceptors are trained to recall specific audio patterns. These patterns can be recombined using conceptor pattern morphing and Boolean operators.

Clustering Conceptors can be used to capture specific concepts in a succinct representation that is especially suitable for efficient clustering. This property has been exploited in multiple domains, such as soccer game analysis [47] and equipment degradation estimation [78].

3 *Word Sense Disambiguation*

This chapter covers the second main theoretical component of this thesis, which is the linguistic problem of word sense disambiguation. Section 3.1 provides a brief overview of the current state of the art in supervised and unsupervised WSD. Section 3.2 provides some context for WSD systems, specifically regarding the hierarchy of granularity that exists within word senses themselves. Section 3.3 lists the most commonly used data suites for WSD.

3.1 *State of the Art*

Approaches for word sense disambiguation can be roughly subdivided into three categories, in chronological order: knowledge-based, supervised, and hybrid methods. The following subsections each gives an overview of one class of methods specifically.

Knowledge-based Systems

Knowledge-based systems rely on lexical knowledge bases (LKBs) to perform their tasks. LKBs are human-annotated data sources that contain a vast amount of lexical information, including sense annotations in the form of sense definitions (*glosses*) and *structural properties* that indicate how different senses relate to one another. The two most common LKBs are WordNet [50] and BabelNet [56], and the most prominent knowledge-based approach to use glosses is the Lesk algorithm [36] which operates on the assumption that words within a given textual neighbourhood (e.g. a paragraph) are likely to share a common meaning. It compares the candidate glosses of an ambiguous target word with the words in its neighbourhood, by looking at the amount of words that occur in the target word's neighbourhood as well as its gloss.

Multiple graph-based algorithms have been proposed, designed to exploit the graph-like nature of the LKBs' structural properties. An example is presented by Agirre, López de Lacalle, and Soroa [1], introducing a method based on the PageRank algorithm [6].

Synsets Lexical knowledge bases represent word senses through *synsets*. This word is a portmanteau for synonym set; it can be seen as a set of words that are interchangeable in some sentential context without changing the truth value of that sentence. As such, it represents the distinct sense that all synonyms in the set refer to. Let us take as example the word *test*, and all noun senses that are encoded in WordNet¹ through different synsets. Those are:

1. trial, trial_run, **test**, tryout;
2. **test**, mental_test, mental_testing, psychometric_test;
3. examination, exam, **test**;
4. **test**, trial;
5. **test**, trial, run;
6. **test**.

¹Source: <http://wordnetweb.princeton.edu/perl/webwn?s=test&sub=Search+WordNet>.

The intention is that the sense represented by a synset can be fully explained by intersecting the sentential contexts of all member synonyms, so as to keep only those sentential contexts wherein *all* synset members can be consistently used. We can see that WordNet partially succeeds in this, notably for the first three synsets. However, the latter three synsets are not easily discernable by its constituent synonyms alone; partially because they contain too little synonyms to begin with, and partially because the synonyms that they do contain, are also used (whether or not in a compound) in other synsets. For completeness, the WordNet glosses of the above synsets are, respectively:

1. Trying something to find out about it;
2. Any standardized procedure for measuring sensitivity or memory or intelligence or aptitude or personality etc;
3. A set of questions or exercises evaluating skill or knowledge;
4. The act of undergoing testing;
5. The act of testing something;
6. A hard outer covering as of some amoebas and sea urchins.

The fact that a synset in itself is not always enough to properly distinguish different senses may be due to the sense *granularity* that is employed in WordNet. This is covered in more detail in Section 3.2.

Supervised Systems

Classical knowledge-based WSD systems have long been the best performing approaches, but have recently been outperformed by *supervised* methods based on language models. These methods rely on pre-trained word embedding models to integrate the required lexical knowledge for WSD into a single vector representation. They then train separate classifiers for every lemma, that takes as input this target word embedding vector, and outputs the probability that the target word is the given lemma.

Word embedding models can be subdivided into two categories: *static* word embedding models only encode information about the word itself into a vector representation, whereas *contextual* models also encode information about the (sentential) context wherein the word is used. A notable example of a static word embedding model is Word2vec [48], and examples for contextual embedding models are ELMo [60] and BERT [11].

Let us take as example the word tank. A static word embedding model would attribute to this word a single vector representation, which is tasked with describing *all* semantics of the word. Example sentences using tank are:

- “As he carefully peeked out of the trench, he saw three tanks approaching.”
- “Wow, that move really did tank our score!”
- “They were happy that the tank out back was still filled to the brim.”
- “After the student’s motivation dwindled, their grades went into the tank.”

The word tank is polysemous, and as such has multiple, more or less distinct meanings. A static embedding model is oblivious of this fact; all the meanings posed above are contained in a single static embedding representing tank. However, according to the distributional hypothesis

Figure 3.1. Example of how the word die is spatially separated in BERT embeddings, using an UMAP projection. Source: Coenen et al. [7, Figure 4].

[49], a word may be assumed to be polysemous if it occurs in different distinct contexts. This property cannot be captured by static word embedding models. A way to alleviate this problem is to combine the static embeddings of all words around the target word into one contextual representation. An overview for different strategies on this can be found in Iacobacci, Pilehvar, and Navigli [23].

Contextual word embedding models directly encode the word's context into the vector representation and as such do not need any kind of auxiliary context encoding. BERT especially is a common tool in the chain of supervised WSD approaches: there is empirical evidence that BERT fits well in the WSD pipeline. BERT has been shown to directly integrate some word sense knowledge into its embeddings [7, 75]; concretely, different word senses of the same word are spatially separated in BERT's embedding space.

An example of this spatial separation is given in Figure 3.1, as listed in Coenen et al. [7]. This figure shows a UMAP [46] projection of BERT embeddings of the word die used in sentences. It can be seen that indeed the different senses for die are separated into distinct spatial clusters. Moreover, there is an apparent quantitative scale that relates to the number of people dying.

Supervised methods can be subdivided into *feature-based* and *fine-tuning* methods. Feature-based methods attach to the final hidden states of the pre-trained word embedding model a word sense classifier that is then trained on some word sense dataset (commonly SemCor [51]). A k -nearest neighbour classifier [9] ($k = 1$) is most commonly used for this task [75]. In contrast, fine-tuning methods train all parameters of the language model during the downstream WSD task and as such fine-tunes a pre-trained model for a concrete task. Loureiro et al. [42] showed that, compared to feature-based methods, fine-tuning methods are more prone to overfitting to the training data. This leads to a higher performance on commonly occurring entries, but lower performance on entries for which the training data is sparse.

Hybrid Systems

The most recent state-of-the-art approaches attempt to attenuate supervised models with the knowledge that can be acquired from LKBs. GlossBERT [22] is a BERT model fine-tuned on a word–gloss matching task (input: sentence with target word + gloss for target word, output: gloss belongs to target word yes/no). SenseBERT [38] completely retrains BERT not only on words but also on their corresponding senses, in an attempt to increase BERT’s implicit semantic knowledge. Both these models achieved then-state-of-the-art performance on a standardised WSD evaluation framework [62].

Another approach to LKB integration is to reduce the amount of unique word senses that needs to be trained on, by compressing the word sense vocabulary. Vial, Lecouteux, and Schwab [71] for example compress the sense vocabulary by taking, for any two word senses, the first descendants of their common ancestor from the word sense hypernymy graph that is encoded in WordNet. By reducing the amount of unique word senses in the vocabulary, the amount of training examples for the remaining word senses increases. This means that the model will have a better chance at training a good representation for all occurring senses.

Kumar et al. [33] introduced the idea to use a continuous *sense embedding* space, instead of a discrete sense labeling space. From an inventory of senses (i.e. WordNet), they create one sense embedding vector per available word sense. The result is a sense embedding space, containing “recipe vectors” for every sense from the inventory. These sense embedding recipe vectors are created with information from WordNet’s structural features, using ConvE [72] to encode graph-based knowledge.

The system, coined EWISE, creates its input CWEs using a BiLSTM model, which are then projected onto the sense embedding space and compared to the sense recipe vectors using a dot product. These comparison scores can then be converted to probability estimates using a softmax layer, or the candidate sense with the highest score can immediately be picked using an argmax.

The model EWISER [4] builds on the ideas used in EWISE. In particular, they introduced a way to encode the relatedness of different concepts through the different types of graph edges found in LKBs. It is worth mentioning that EWISER achieved one of the best scores in the integrated comparison of Loureiro et al. [42].

For a global overview the reader is referred to Loureiro et al. [42, Table 1], who have performed an integrated comparison of the currently best performing WSD systems. As they note, many current approaches integrate but a part of the word sense knowledge present in LKBs like WordNet. For example, GlossBERT only looks at gloss knowledge, whereas the sense vocabulary compression methods purely rely on structural features. A notable exception is EWISER, which has the capability to integrate many structural features as well as glosses into a single system.

Unsupervised Word Sense Clustering

To partition an arbitrary cloud of word embeddings into distinct senses, an unsupervised disambiguation method is required as there is no complete sense vocabulary available. Unfortunately, this approach is not a main focus in the current state of the art of word senses disambiguation. During the presentation of SenseBERT, Levine et al. [38] briefly mentioned how their model

Table 3.1. Examples of coarse-grained and fine-grained sense sets, taken from WordNet (**mouse**, **pick**). The sense from the word “mouse” are more coarse-grained than the senses from the word “pick”. For the sake of this example, only noun senses were considered.

Lemma	WordNet Gloss	Example
mouse#1	any of numerous small rodents typically resembling diminutive rats having pointed snouts and small ears on elongated bodies with slender usually hairless tails	<i>“she has a pet mouse living in a cage”</i>
mouse#4	a hand-operated electronic device that controls the coordinates of a cursor on your computer screen as you move it around on a pad; on the bottom of the device is a ball that rolls on the surface of the pad	<i>“a mouse takes much more room than a trackball”</i>
pick#1	the person or thing chosen or selected	<i>“he was my pick for mayor”</i>
pick#9	the act of choosing or selecting	<i>“you can take your pick”</i>

could be suitable for unsupervised sense clustering due to the fact that they encode word sense knowledge directly into the embeddings themselves. This was marked as future research.

3.2 Granularity in WSD

Word senses exist within a hierarchy of granularity: some senses are only subtly different, whereas other senses differ enormously. A coarser grained set of senses has a wide focus and its senses are often easily distinguished. Contrastingly, finer grained sets of senses often have a more narrow focus and it becomes increasingly hard even for humans to correctly disambiguate between them. Table 3.1 shows examples for coarse-grained sense sets for the word “mouse”, and fine-grained sense sets for the word “pick”. One can see the subtle difference between the two senses for “pick”, whereas these two senses for “mouse” pertain to completely different entities that will almost never be confused.

Most WSD contributions keep to the sense granularity that was used in their training and testing data, mostly based sense data from WordNet. Despite that, it is argued that the sense inventory of WordNet has a granularity that is too fine and sense distinctions that are too subtle to form a direct basis for WSD evaluation datasets [34, 42, 75]. Edmonds and Kilgarriff [12] argue that this might be due to WordNet’s thesaurus-design, that is, grouping words per sense in a set of synonyms (*synsets*). This one sense–multiple words paradigm might focus attention on word similarity. Contrastingly, a dictionary design, that is, grouping senses per word in a set of homographs (words that have multiple meanings but the same spelling²), might imply

²In contrast to homonyms, i.e. words that have multiple meanings but the same *pronunciation*. For example, desert is a homograph but no homonym, as “to desert” is pronounced differently than “the desert”.

a focus on the sense partitioning of a word. Intuitively, the latter would make more sense for WSD, where the goal is precisely to identify these different word senses.

There are many papers that propose some hierarchical levels of sense granularity. Most contributions make the distinction between “fine” and “coarse” [42, e.g.], yet what either label entails precisely remains unclear. Palmer, Babko-Malaya, and Dang [57] propose three different levels of sense granularity, specifically for verb senses and based on WordNet:

fine Direct WordNet senses;

- Sense groupings: groups of semantically similar WordNet senses;

coarse Framesets: sets of sense groupings where syntactic alternations of the same word are combined (e.g. “leave”, as in “to depart” or “to leave behind”).

Resnik and Yarowsky [64] identify four different levels of granularity to classify sense similarity:

coarse Homograph level (e.g. “band”, as in “group” or “ring”);

- Major sense level (e.g. band#group as in “music group” or “other group”);
- Subsense level (which they use to disambiguate between a major sense and an arbitrary specialisation of that sense);

fine Subsubsense level (to disambiguate between different, arbitrary specialisations of the same major sense).

However, they did not specify how especially the lower granularity levels were built up — in fact, they explicitly stated that the specialisation from any major sense to a subsense was arbitrary.

3.3 Training and Testing Datasets for WSD

Sense-annotated Training Corpora

Most model-based WSD approaches use SemCor [51] as training dataset. SemCor contains 352 texts from the Brown Corpus [15], originally sense-annotated with senses from WordNet version 1.6. Later on, these senses were mapped to the most recent WordNet 3.0 senses. SemCor is the *de facto* training dataset for supervised or hybrid WSD approaches, containing around 250 thousand sense-tagged nouns, verbs and adjectives. It may be noted that SemCor contains sparse data: it provides a limited number of examples per sense [42]. A logical result is that it covers a lot of distinct senses: more than 33 thousand in total.

More recently, Lacerra et al. [34] presented the Coarse Sense Inventory (CSI), wherein WordNet’s synsets are mapped to coarser tagsets. These mappings can then be used to create coarser labels for e.g. SemCor data. The CSI covers about 78% of SemCor’s annotated instances.

Another corpus that can be used for WSD training is OMSTI (One Million Sense-Tagged Instances, [70]), which is an automatically constructed collection of sense-tagged words based on the MultiUN corpus [13]. Senses are sourced from WordNet 3.0 directly. This dataset is much larger, containing just shy of a million sense annotations. The corpus covers only 4 thousand distinct senses however, indicating that every sense is very well represented but the vocabulary in total might be limited as compared to for instance SemCor.

Evaluation Frameworks and Test Sets

For evaluating the performance of a WSD system, Raganato, Camacho-Collados, and Navigli [62] provide an integrated WSD evaluation framework. This framework consists of multiple evaluation datasets from the SemEval³ and Senseval⁴ competitions. Five datasets⁵ are included in the evaluation framework, each ranging from 455 to 2282 annotations of varying difficulty. All sense annotations were sourced from WordNet, originally with varying versions, but eventually mapped to the correct WordNet 3.0 senses. As WordNet acts as a basis for all these sets, they are by default of the finer-grained variety. Note however that the sense annotations of these data sets can also be mapped to coarser tagsets using the Coarse Sense Inventory. This was done in Loureiro et al. [42], for example.

CoarseWSD-20

Loureiro et al. [42] introduced CoarseWSD-20, a coarse-grained WSD dataset built up of only 20 different nouns, each manually selected. After selecting these 20 words, all representative sentences using those words were extracted from Wikipedia. The result is a group of datasets of sense-ambiguous sentences per word, ranging in size from some hundreds to some thousands exemplars.

This dataset was designed to train model-based WSD systems in the best possible situation. This mostly entails the scenario where there exists ample training data for every lemma. Additionally, the words were selected so that their senses are easily distinguishable (i.e. coarse).

³<https://semeval.github.io/>

⁴<http://web.eecs.umich.edu/~mihalcea/senseval/>

⁵Viz.: Senseval-2; Senseval-3 task 1; SemEval-07 task 17; SemEval-13 task 12; SemEval-15 task 13.

PART III
METHODOLOGY

4 Implementation

This chapter presents the abstraction hierarchy extraction method that was implemented for this thesis. It was decided to use the pre-trained EWISER model as the word sense disambiguation system, and thus use WordNet 3.0 as sense vocabulary.

Section 4.1 gives a global overview of the implemented pipeline. In the interest of brevity some implementation details are omitted there; these will be covered in Section 4.2 and Chapter 5.

4.1 A Global Overview of the Pipeline

Before going into the developed pipeline itself, let us first define its input and output format as well as its performance criterion. The pipeline requires two forms of input: firstly, a set of target nouns from which we want to distil abstraction relations, each required to be contained in WordNet 3.0, and secondly, a large unlabeled corpus of sentences using the given target nouns. The pipeline's output is a dense weighted graph such that every node represents one word sense extracted from the list of target nouns, and an edge between two nodes represents the level of abstraction between these two senses, reflected by the edge weight. The pipeline's performance will be evaluated based on its degree of alignment with word hyponymy and the logical subsumption model. In addition, it will be subjected to cognitive and discourse analysis.

Let us now consider the pipeline itself. It can be subdivided into six stages, which are the following:

I Parts-of-speech tagging, initial filtering

Firstly, the corpus sentences were completely POS-tagged using the spaCy v3 [52] pre-trained natural language processing pipeline. In English, many nouns can also be used as a verb. Remember for example the example word *plant* from Section 1.1, which can be used as a noun but also as a verb to denote the act of putting plants or seeds into the ground. Since for the current experiment we focus only on the target words used as nouns, an initial filtering was done so that only sentences that use the target words as a noun were kept.

II Flattening

We are now left with a collection of sentences wherein one or more target nouns are used in some sense. The next step is to normalise this collection into *single entries* for every target noun occurrence. This entails that a sentence wherein two target nouns are used — be it different target nouns or the same noun twice, whether or not used in the same sense — should be duplicated into one entry for the first target noun occurrence, and another entry for the second target noun occurrence.

The resulting output is a collection of noun–sentence pairs, each one corresponding to a single occurrence of the given noun in the given sentence.

III Word sense classification

The resulting set of noun–sentence pairs were then fed into a word sense classification system using the EWISER [4] model. As the target nouns were chosen so that they are all

contained within WordNet, and EWISER was trained on SemCor which uses WordNet synsets as vocabulary, all target nouns are guaranteed to be within EWISER’s vocabulary.

The EWISER model maps a noun–sentence pair into the target noun’s WordNet synset, which are used in the present pipeline to represent lemmata. Thus, the EWISER output was processed such that the noun–sentence pairs are mapped into lemma–sentence pairs.

IV Synset-grouping, calculation of CWEs

A pre-trained BERT model was employed to create contextual word embeddings from the lemma–sentence pairs. The lemma–sentence pairs were thus mapped into lemma–CWE pairs. This step is detailed in Section 5.3.

A state matrix X_ℓ was then constructed for every lemma $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ (where \mathcal{L} is the set of distinct lemmata extracted from the word sense classification process). The matrix X_ℓ is an $N \times L_\ell$ matrix that contains the concatenated CWEs of the given lemma. Here, N corresponds to the embedding dimensionality of BERT (where $N = d_{\text{BERT}} = 768$), and L_ℓ corresponds to the number of occurrences of lemma ℓ in the target sentences.

V Conceptor calculation, pairwise abstraction estimation

The state matrices X_ℓ could now be transformed into conceptors $C_\ell = C(R_\ell, \alpha)$, where $R_\ell = X_\ell(X_\ell)^\top / L_\ell$ is the correlation matrix of X_ℓ and with an aperture parameter α that is constant across all lemmata.

A relaxed variant on the Löwner order, $\succ: C_N \times C_N \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, was used to estimate the abstraction relation between any two conceptors. It can be interpreted as follows:

- Lemma μ is more abstract than lemma ν iff $\succ(C_\mu, C_\nu) \gg 0$;
- Lemma μ is less abstract than lemma ν iff $\succ(C_\mu, C_\nu) \ll 0$;
- There is no abstraction relation between lemmas μ and ν iff $\succ(C_\mu, C_\nu) \approx 0$.

An important property of the fuzzy extension is that it is still irreflexive and antisymmetric, i.e. $\succ(C_\mu, C_\mu) = 0$ and $\succ(C_\mu, C_\nu) = -\succ(C_\nu, C_\mu)$.

The output of this stage is defined as a pairwise abstraction matrix $A \in [-1, 1]^{|\mathcal{L}| \times |\mathcal{L}|}$ such that $A_{i,j} = \succ(C_{\ell_i}, C_{\ell_j})$. The process of estimating a suitable α , as well as the formal definition of \succ , are described in Section 4.2.

VI Generation of abstraction graphs

From the declared \succ we can create a weighted, directed graph \mathcal{G} that encodes all estimated abstraction relations:

$$\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{E}, \succ), \quad (4.1)$$

where the edge set \mathcal{E} is defined in terms of \succ : $\mathcal{E} = \{(\mu, \nu) \in \mathcal{L}^2 \mid \succ(\mu, \nu) > 0\}$. The simplest way to create such a graph is by interpreting the clamped $A_{\geq 0} = \max(A, 0)$ as an *adjacency matrix* which describes \mathcal{G} . Due to the antisymmetry of \succ , the pairwise abstraction matrix is antisymmetric as well, implying that $A = -A^\top$. This fact ensures that \mathcal{G} is *non-destructive*, i.e. no information is lost when describing \succ in terms of \mathcal{G} .

It is also possible to extract a regular but destructive binary abstraction relation

$$R_t = \{(\mu, \nu) \in \mathcal{L}^2 \mid \succ(\mu, \nu) > t\}, \quad (4.2)$$

with corresponding graph

$$\mathcal{G}_t = (\mathcal{L}, R_t, \succ), \quad (4.3)$$

for some threshold value $t \in [0, 1]$. Note that \mathcal{G} can be seen as a special case of \mathcal{G}_t with $t = 0$, i.e. $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_0$.

The pipeline is depicted in full in Figure 4.1.

4.2 Conceptor Calculation and Abstraction Estimation

In stage **V**, state matrices are combined into conceptors and these are subsequently used to estimate conceptor-to-conceptor abstraction. The following sections cover these processes in more detail.

Aperture Setting

Let us first take a closer look at the aperture setting α that is used for the calculation of conceptor matrices in stage **V**. This requires a carefully considered value for α , so that the conceptors can adequately reflect differences in abstraction. As shown in Section 2.1, an aperture value that is too high will lead to conceptor matrices where all singular values are close to one, limiting expressivity. Contrastingly, an aperture value that is too low will lead to conceptors with near-zero singular values. This section proposes a method for deciding on an aperture value that attempts to maximise expressivity.

Let us recall that aperture plays a part in scaling the singular values of the point cloud's state correlation matrix so that they range in $[0, 1]$, using the function $s_i = f(\alpha, \sigma_i) = \sigma_i / (\sigma_i + \alpha^{-2})$. We can see that, for positive real x , $\lim_{x \uparrow \infty} f(\alpha, x) = 1$ and $\lim_{x \uparrow \infty} \frac{d}{dx} f(\alpha, x) = 0$, where the value for α determines how quickly f and f' grow to 1 and 0 respectively. The intuition behind the proposed method is to pick a value for α such that the largest singular value σ_{\max} of the correlation matrix can still be adequately distinguished from the second-largest singular value $\sigma_{\max-1}$. The term ‘‘adequately’’ is rather vague, and indeed it corresponds to a parameter in the method for estimating such an aperture value. The idea is to pick an aperture α value such that $f(\alpha, \sigma_{\max}) + t = 1$, for some small tolerance value $t \in (0, 1]$. Solving for α in $f(\alpha, \sigma_{\max}) + t = 1$ yields:

$$\frac{\sigma_{\max}}{\sigma_{\max} + \alpha^{-2}} + t = 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{1-t}}{\sqrt{t} \sqrt{\sigma_{\max}}}. \quad (4.4)$$

Let us define this aperture setting function as $\alpha_t^* : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. It is important to note that as t becomes larger we start losing scaling ‘‘bandwidth’’: the range of $f(\alpha_t^*(\sigma_{\max}), \cdot)$ is equal to $[0, 1 - t]$.

Definition of a Graded Löwner-Orderedness Estimator

We declared the graded extension of the Löwner order $\succ : \mathcal{C}_N \times \mathcal{C}_N \rightarrow [-1, 1]$. This section formally defines it, and attempts to provide an explanation for the intuition behind it. Let us recall the definition of the binary Löwner order. This is a partial order \leq such that, for any two positive semi-definite $N \times N$ matrices X and Y , $X \leq Y$ if and only if $Y - X$ is positive semidefinite. This implies that extending the Löwner order to the fuzzy domain is equivalent to finding a metric of ‘‘positive definiteness’’, i.e. a metric on how close a matrix is to being positive semidefinite.

Figure 4.1. An overview of the proposed pipeline.

A matrix is positive semidefinite if and only if it is symmetric and all its eigenvalues are nonnegative. The symmetry condition is met by definition, for conceptors are positive semidefinite and the property of symmetry is carried over to a matrix difference if all operands are symmetric. It is therefore the magnitude of the difference matrix's eigenvalues that we can use to express the extent with which it approaches positive semidefiniteness.

Let us consider two arbitrary conceptors C_μ and C_ν and their difference matrix $D = C_\mu - C_\nu$, and define $\bar{\lambda}(D) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i(D)/N$ as the mean magnitude of D 's eigenvalues. This value was used directly as heuristic in Bricman [5], yet the mean difference matrix eigenvalue magnitude correlates with the amount of lemma exemplar occurrences, when they are below $N = d_{\text{BERT}}$.

When $L_\mu < N$, the correlation matrix R_μ created from X_μ will have a rank of $k \leq L_\mu$. Consequently, C_μ will as well have rank k , which implies that it has exactly k nonzero singular values. Let us now also assume that also $L_\nu < N$. By the subadditivity of matrix rank, we find that the difference matrix $C_\mu - C_\nu$ has at most $\min(L_\mu + L_\nu, N)$ nonzero singular values. When L_μ and L_ν are both significantly smaller than N , the difference matrix will become singular and as such impact the value for the mean eigenvalue magnitude heuristic. This is undesirable.

The definition for \succ that is used in this thesis can be seen as an extension of the candidate definition defined above, ignoring null eigenvalues. It is defined as follows:

$$\succ(C_\mu, C_\nu) = 2 \cdot \frac{\bar{\lambda}_+(C_\mu - C_\nu)}{\bar{\lambda}_+(C_\mu - C_\nu) + \bar{\lambda}_-(C_\mu - C_\nu)} - 1, \quad (4.5)$$

where:

- $\bar{\lambda}_+(C_\mu - C_\nu)$ corresponds to mean magnitude of all positive eigenvalues of $C_\mu - C_\nu$;
- $\bar{\lambda}_-(C_\mu - C_\nu)$ corresponds to mean magnitude of all negative eigenvalues of $C_\mu - C_\nu$.

Thus, \succ calculates the positive–negative eigenvalue magnitude ratio of the conceptors' difference matrix, scaled to fall between -1 and 1 . This equation is antisymmetric as declared in the description of stage **V**. This was asserted through preliminary numerical analysis on conceptors extracted from the CoarseWSD-20 dataset.

5 *Experimental Setup*

This chapter explains how the pipeline described in Chapter 4 is used in this thesis to answer the research questions. It covers all operational details, including the used datasets in Section 5.1, noteworthy code packages that were used, etc. The remaining sections focus on the experimental setup for: the EWISER implementation in Section 5.2; the CWE system in Section 5.3; conceptor calculation in Section 5.4; and finally graph generation in Section 5.5. The source code that was used to conduct all experiments is available at <https://github.com/jesper-sk/msc-thesis-ai-imp>.

5.1 *Datasets*

As described in Section 4.1, the pipeline requires two sets of data:

1. A large corpus of regular English sentences;
2. A set of nouns, used in the aforementioned corpus, for which we want to estimate abstraction relations.

Note that this excludes the pre-training data of the models that are used in some pipeline stages, more details on these follow in later sections. The sections that follow now go over the concrete datasets that were used with the developed pipeline.

Set of Sentences

For dataset 1 the BookCorpus [79] is used, specifically the dataset that is available through Hugging Face’s datasets package [39]. This dataset combines sentences from 11 thousand English books, to create a set of 74 million sentences. This dataset has become one of the *de facto* corpora for high quality natural English text.

Set of Nouns

The nouns that constitute dataset 2 were hand-picked to adhere to the following constraints. They should all: a) be used in the sentences of dataset 1; b) be contained within WordNet 3.0, as specified in Section 4.1; c) share a semantic frame; and d) be polysemous, i.e. have multiple senses, some of which may have a different semantic frame.

A semantic frame can be seen as a thematic subject with which all target nouns are semantically related. The constraint of having such a frame was added to ensure that there will an intuitive abstraction hierarchy present, with which to compare the extracted hierarchies from the pipeline. Constraint d) was added for proper evaluation of the word sense disambiguation stage of the developed pipeline, cf. research question *i*.

The nouns were picked from the WSD Evaluation Framework, which made sure that the latter two constraints were adhered to. A total of 129 nouns were picked in total, which occurred – in singular or plural form – in 1.6 million BookCorpus sentences. The exact nouns that were picked, are listed in appendix C.1.

Figure 5.1. The global architecture of EWISER. Source: Bevilacqua and Navigli [4, Figure 1].

5.2 Word Sense Disambiguation

For the word sense disambiguation stage (stage III) the EWISER model [4] was used, as it has state-of-the-art performance on the WSD task at the time of writing this thesis.

Figure 5.1 shows the general architecture of EWISER. The sentence with a target word is first passed into a frozen BERT model to extract a contextual word embedding, which is then passed into a feed-forward network that projects this CWE onto the synset embedding space. This embedding vector is then compared with recipe embeddings for all candidate synsets using a dot product, resulting in “hidden” synset embedding scores (z). These scores are summed with the scores of all related synsets (decided through an LKB structural features graph), multiplied by their respective edge weights. The final result (q), called *logit*, then represents the classification quality of the candidate synset.

The source code from EWISER was taken from the repository available at <https://github.com/SapienzaNLP/ewiser> and was altered to be compatible with the rest of the implementation suite. The pipeline employs a pre-trained EWISER model using the weight checkpoints “SemCor + tagged glosses + WordNet Examples,” available through [the same repository](https://github.com/SapienzaNLP/ewiser). The EWISER model was run on the GPU (Nvidia GTX 1080) with a batch size of 16. The fork of the original source code that was used for this experiment is available at <https://github.com/jesper-sk/ewiser>. The EWISER model was built to fit in the `en_core_web_sm`¹ pipeline that is available through Explosion’s spaCy python package [52], and which also includes POS-tagging functionality. The EWISER model takes as input the target sentences along with the location of the target noun herein, and gives as output the target word’s POS tag along with its classified WordNet synset (i.e. the synset with the highest logit value q). The pipeline uses the EWISER model pre-trained with optimal weights, as evaluated in Bevilacqua and Navigli [4] on the WSD evaluation framework. For structural features, the model uses a graph encoding synset hypernymy as well as hyponymy, extracted from WordNet.

¹Installation instructions can be found at https://spacy.io/models/en#en_core_web_sm.

Figure 5.2. Structure of the BERT-based vectorisation pipeline.

5.3 Contextual Word Embedding

In stage **IV**, the target nouns used in the given sentences are embedded into a contextual vector representation using a pre-trained BERT model. The BERT model was chosen due to its proven performance in semantic understanding and its role as basis for many complex downstream language understanding tasks [22, 38, 41, 71]. Additionally, there is empiric evidence that BERT is able to integrate semantic knowledge directly into its embeddings [7, 75]. This section describes how the BERT model is implemented, and how it was used to extract CWEs.

Figure 5.2 shows the global structure of the BERT setup as it was used for the present experiments. This setup follows the setups used in the aforementioned literature. An input sentence was first tokenized into whole or, for compound words, subword tokens. To this token string was prepended the fixed [CLS] token, indicating the start of an input sequence, and appended the [SEP] token, indicating to BERT the ending of the sequence². The resulting sequence of tokens was then padded so that every sentence in the batch has a token sequence of equal length. If necessary, the sequences were truncated in order to match BERT’s input size. An initial WordPiece [67] embedding vector was made for every token, which is the *de facto* embedding system used in BERT [11]. The input for the BERT model is the WordPiece embedding summed with a position embedding, used to maintain token ordering inside the model.

The batch of encoded sentences was then fed into the BERT model. Following a heuristic that is introduced in Devlin et al. [11], a target word’s output embedding was calculated by performing a weighted sum on the activations of the final four hidden layers. If the target word

²Note that in BERT it is possible to have another sentence after the initial [SEP] token, which is used for pairs of sentences in e.g. question answering systems. This feature is unused in the current experiments.

comprises multiple subword tokens, the constituent subword CWEs were averaged to form a single full-word target CWE. This practice is used in for example Wiedemann et al. [75].

The base uncased model $BERT_{BASE}$ was used, which has twelve layers, a hidden size of 768 and twelve self-attention heads. The total amount of trainable parameters is equal to 110 million. The pipeline employs the BERT model and its weights that were made available in Hugging Face’s transformers package [77], under the identifier “bert-base-uncased”. The model and tokenizer were run on the GPU (Nvidia GTX 1080) with a batch size of 24.

5.4 *Conceptors*

All conceptor-related functionality was implemented manually based on array programming and linear algebra methods available in python’s NumPy package [20]. An important consideration of digital computation of conceptor-related methods is the imprecision of IEEE 754 floating-point arithmetic [54]. This consideration requires us to allow for small deviations whenever a variable x needs to be checked for equality to a value c – if the value of x is calculated with floating-point arithmetic, it could occur that it formally ought to be equal to c but in fact is set equal to the nearest IEEE 754-representable value. This is important in e.g. the calculation of the graded Löwner order extension \succ , where eigenvalues are checked for equality to 0. In the experimental setup, a deviation of at most 0.001 was allowed, i.e. $x \approx c$ if and only if $c - 0.001 < x < c + 0.001$.

For the calculation of conceptors, the aperture estimation method as specified in Section 4.2 was used by manually calculating correlation matrices of the CWEs of a subset of the target nouns, and calculating their maximal singular values. A tolerance value of $t = 0.01$ was used, which was deemed to give a good middle ground between expressiveness and scaling bandwidth. This led to an estimated aperture value of $\alpha = 0.58$.

5.5 *Graph Calculation*

The python package networkx [19] was used for the calculation, representation and analysis of the graphs in stage VI. This package also includes an implementation for calculating the transitive closure of a directed acyclic graph.

PART IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6 Results

The pipeline discussed in Chapter 4 was run with the dataset and configuration as listed in Chapter 5. The current chapter provides results in the form of visualisations and analysis of the pipeline’s output. Section 6.1 covers quantitative results of the Löwner order extension, and Section 6.2 specifically evaluates the extent with which this extension can be seen as transitive. Notably, the generation of abstraction graphs is done in Chapter 7, as this is best fitted within a discussion context.

6.1 Output of the Pipeline

The word sense disambiguation stage of the pipeline classified the contextual word embeddings of 128 target nouns, as used in the contexts of 1.6 million sentences, into 302 distinct synsets. A first important observation is that this classification function is neither injective nor surjective: a synset may comprise of CWEs from multiple distinct target nouns, and CWEs from a single target noun may be classified as different synsets. This implies that the pipeline strictly does not do abstraction comparison on the *lemma* level (a single word pertaining to a single sense), but on the *sense* level.

Conceptors were created from the 302 clouds of contextual word embeddings, which were then compared in a pairwise manner using the fuzzy Löwner order extension \succ . Figures 6.1 and 6.2 show pairwise abstraction matrices for these synset subsets. The shown matrices only show inter-synset abstraction between synsets that share a common theme, in this instance trees (Figure 6.1), foodstuffs and plants (both in Figure 6.2). This was done to split the large pairwise abstraction matrix up into smaller, legible and interpretable visualisations. These themes were determined purely intuitively. For each plot, the synsets are ordered into three intuitive levels of abstraction, with level 1 being the most concrete, and level 3 the most abstract. In addition, a single group of synsets is included in every plot that form meronymous (part-of) relations. These groups were determined subjectively by the author and merely act to improve plot readability.

A Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated to evaluate the relationship between average synset abstraction level and the number of synset occurrences in the corpus. They were found to be positively related: $r(300) = .34, p < .001$. This finding will be discussed in detail in Section 7.2.

6.2 On the Transitivity of \succ

Given the non-trivial formulation of \succ , it was not possible to assert its transitivity by definition. This section explores whether this property is present in \succ on the data that was used in the current thesis.

Through numerical analysis we find that R_t , as defined in stage VI, is transitive for any $t \in [0, 1]$, i.e. for any distinct triplet $\mu, \nu, \xi \in \mathcal{L}$ we find that $\mu R_t \nu$ and $\nu R_t \xi$ implies $\mu R_t \xi$. Given that \succ is irreflexive and antisymmetric by definition, we can conclude that R_t can be interpreted as a strict partial order $\prec_t := R_t$.

Figure 6.1. Pairwise abstraction matrix for a subset of extracted synsets, all from the theme "trees". Also included are the synsets' occurrences in the BookCorpus sentences (note that they are listed in logarithmic scale). The synsets are ordered on their intuitive abstraction or meronymy level. For the synset labels, the appended index is equal to the synset index of the given word, and corresponds with the WordNet synset index. These are also listed in Appendix C.2.

We can also make a fuzzy extension of transitivity and apply that to \succ directly. For this we borrow some definitions from fuzzy set and relation theory [80]. In regular set theory, any given item x can either be a member of a set A or not a member of the set, i.e. either $x \in A$ or $x \notin A$. This membership function is not so clear-cut (or *crisp*) for fuzzy sets; instead, for a fuzzy set B on a universe U , we define a *membership function* $\mu_B : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that defines the *extent with which* any item $u \in U$ is part of B . The universe can be seen as the (crisp) set of all relevant items.

Let us now move to fuzzy relation theory. For a fuzzy relation R on a crisp universe U we again define a membership function $\mu_R : U^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that defines the extent with which a pair of items are related. Notably, such a function corresponds to our Löwner order estimator \succ when restricting the domain to only include the edges from our graph \mathcal{G} , i.e. $\succ|_{\mathcal{E}}$. By definition, this restricted variant of \succ restricts its codomain to $[0, 1]$.

Finally, let us define a fuzzy extension of transitivity, i.e. a property of fuzzy relations that attempts to extend on the notion of transitivity for crisp relations.

Definition 4 (Triangular norm). *A triangular norm (t-norm) is an increasing, associative and commutative mapping $T : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that satisfies $T(1, x) = x$ for all $x \in [0, 1]$.*

Figure 6.2. Pairwise abstraction matrices for synset-subsets: *top* foodstuffs; *bottom* plants.

With a t-norm we can define T -transitivity:

Definition 5 (T -transitivity). *For a given t-norm T and crisp universe set U , a fuzzy relation R on U^2 with membership function $\mu_R : U^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is T -transitive if and only if:*

$$\forall (x, y), (y, z), (x, z) \in U^2 \quad \mu_R(x, z) \geq T(\mu_R(x, y), \mu_R(y, z)).$$

Many different t-norms exist, including but not limited to:

1. max–min norm: $T(x, y) = \min(x, y)$;
2. Algebraic product: $T(x, y) = x \cdot y$;
3. Łukasiewicz norm: $T(x, y) = \max(x + y - 1, 0)$.

All t-norms have different properties and attempt to provide the fuzzy extension of general transitivity in some way, and fail to do so in other ways [30]. The extent of this topic is beyond the scope of this thesis – entire books are written just on triangular norms [31].

Through numerical analysis with definitions 4 and 5 we find that, when we treat $\succ_{|\varepsilon}$ as membership function for the fuzzy abstraction relation on the crisp universe \mathcal{L}^2 , it is max–min-, product- and Łukasiewicz-transitive.

7 Discussion

In this chapter, we dive deeper into the results that were first presented in Chapter 6. Section 7.1 covers observations that were made of the sentences in the BookCorpus, and their impact in the word sense classification stage specifically. Section 7.2 goes over how the amount of synset occurrences impacts the abstraction values of this synset. We finally extract abstraction hierarchies from the pairwise abstraction matrices in Section 7.3. The last two sections cover some broader observations and deficits of the developed pipeline; Section 7.4 attempts to shed a light on how logical or linguistic intuition can deviate from empirical-statistical abstraction relations that were extracted from the present corpus, and Section 7.5 covers the closed-world assumption under which the pipeline operates.

For this chapter, in the interest of brevity the expressions $\succ(\mu, \nu)$ with $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{L}$, and $\succ(\text{foo}, \text{bar})$ are used to denote $\succ(C_\mu, C_\nu)$ and $\succ(C_{\text{foo}}, C_{\text{bar}})$, respectively.

7.1 Observations on the Word Sense Classification Stage

The unlabeled nature of the BookCorpus dataset prevents us from quantifying the performance of this stage, but it is still possible to give insight into the general behaviour of the WSD stage on this corpus. Upon manual inspection of the classification results, there are various observations that can be extracted. These are described in the sections that follow.

Named Entities

Some words not only have multiple senses, but can also be used to name entities such as humans, animals or other objects. Examples from the used target noun set include rose, daisy, berry, ash, daffodil and willow. These words can all be used as a person's or animal's name. The EWISER model is incapable of recognising these named entities, and instead incorrectly classifies these as belonging to one of the WordNet synsets. A more specific example is blackberry, where any exemplar referring to a Blackberry phone is classified as the blackberry fruit ([blackberry.n.01](#)).

This problem could be alleviated by adding a Named Entity Recognition (NER) stage to the pipeline, which can be used to pre-emptively filter out any named entities. NER is a common and well-defined task in computational linguistics, and with an accompanying dataset known as the CoNLL-2003 shared task [66]. Pre-trained cased BERT models fine-tuned on this task are available through the `transformers` package.¹ Another, perhaps simpler approach would be to move to cased variants of the used models (e.g. `bert-base-cased` for BERT), and cased datasets. Named entities are capitalised, and would as such be detectable for a non-case-agnostic pipeline.

Compound Words

A sequence of words together can sometimes form a compound, and as such have a different meaning altogether. More specifically, *open compounds* are those compounds where its con-

¹For example, <https://huggingface.co/dslim/bert-base-NER>

stituents are separated by a space. Concrete examples of target words that have open compounds in the current corpus are:

- apple in Adam’s_apple;
- coffee in coffee_table;
- berry in holly_berry and yew_berry;
- orange in orange_juice;
- fruit in passion_fruit;
- garden in garden_of_Eden;

It is expected that more of such open compounds remain undetected in the 1.6 million sentences that were used for this thesis. The present pipeline initially tokenises all sentences to word- or subword-level tokens before passing them to the word sense classification stage as individual inputs. This implies that the pipeline is not able to detect such open compound words. As a result, for all sentences that use Adam’s_apple, the pipeline incorrectly classifies the word apple as referring to the fruit. All these examples have the potential to skew the resulting conceptors.

Future research could focus on supporting multi-word lemmata in the pipeline. Merging full word tokens to form a single CWE can be achieved simply by extending the existing subword token merge operation. The main challenge then lies in the detection of these open compounds in the input corpus. This might be nontrivial, as the human interpretation of open compounds is affected by sentential context as well as the semantic relationship between constituents and the occurrence (in)frequency of the compound [16, 37]. An example for automatic extraction of open compounds can be found in Sornlertlamvanich and Tanaka [69].

Metaphors and Metonyms

A metaphor is a well-known form of rhetoric where one thing (the *tenor*) is referred to by mentioning another, altogether unrelated thing (the *vehicle*); in doing so, one ascribes a subset of the vehicle’s attributes or properties to the tenor. In the common example “All the world’s a stage” from Shakespeare’s *As You Like It*, world is the tenor and stage the vehicle. This might pose a problem in the current pipeline when the vehicle word is a target noun, since it is not used to refer to the strict meaning of the vehicle. Indeed, it is just a mere *vehicle* for a set of attributes that one means to ascribe to the tenor. The meaning is therefore different from that word as it is used regularly to refer to itself.

Metonymy is subtly different. It is still the process where one thing is referred to through another thing, however metonymy is not a mere rhetorical technique. Instead, it is a cognitive process in which one conceptual entity is mentally accessed via another entity [35, 58]. For example, when we use the sentence “you smell of roses”, we mean to refer to the scent or aroma that is typically associated with roses. To use the terminology from above, roses is a vehicle for accessing that specific property. As the tenor in the metonymic process is implicit (for it relies on a pre-existing cognitive or semantic relationship between the vehicle and the tenor), this phenomenon is especially dangerous for the word sense classification system.

Some examples of metaphors and metonyms found in the BookCorpus are:

- “[...] the only scents she smelled in the morning was *coffee*, [...]”
- “[...] pale blond hair and eyes the color of the *flowers* that dominated [...]”

- “you look like an anemic *grape*”
- “[...] a bizarre outfit of turquoise and *grape* with an embroidered *grape* bolero vest [...]”
- “[...] she had a face pinched like a withered *fig*”
- “[...] the green of both ocean and *forest* in his eyes, [...]”

While the effects of these processes may be subtle in terms of meaning, it will still have an impact on the embeddings for vehicle words. Since the used embedding models are explicitly *contextual*, it may be well possible that they are able to extract the qualities or properties that are accessed through the vehicle from the meaning of the vehicle itself, and as such create an embedding that only envelopes these qualities. Future research could attempt to explain how contextual embedding models such as BERT do or do not react to metaphors and metonyms, by inspecting the vector embedding space created for metaphoric or metonymic sentences.

Sense Granularity

In Section 3.2, we have seen that the WordNet vocabulary of senses is commonly seen as relatively fine, which has a negative impact on word sense disambiguation accuracy — even humans have trouble disambiguating some senses present in WordNet. This fact has no direct impact for the experiments done in this thesis, as the pipeline was run on a manually curated set of target nouns. Moreover, from the resulting set of 302 synsets only a small number are visualised and interpreted here. As a result, synsets that may not be easily discernable but are still present in the extracted synset-set (e.g. the twelve synsets for thing: [thing.n.01](#) to [thing.n.12](#)) are largely ignored for the current experiments. The impact of sense granularity on average synset abstraction is therefore marked as future research.

7.2 *The Impact of Synset Occurrence Count*

There is a significant correlation between the amount of synset occurrences and the synset’s average abstraction level. In the large pairwise abstraction matrices that are shown in Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2, we can see that synsets with low occurrence counts (for example, [corn_whiskey.n.01](#), [blush_wine.n.01](#), [radish_plant.n.01](#), and [rocket.n.03](#)) also have exceptionally low abstraction values across the board. Conversely, the inverse effect can not be observed: synsets with an exceptionally high occurrence such as [tree.n.01](#) do not have exceptionally high abstraction values.

Figure 7.1 shows how the synsets’ average abstraction values change with synset occurrence count. We can see that, for synsets with less than approximately one hundred occurrences, the average abstraction value scales almost linearly with synset occurrence. After this threshold, the correlation becomes less apparent. We might therefore conclude that synsets’ abstraction is impacted towards lower values when their occurrence count is below a threshold which we now tentatively put at one hundred occurrences. It is noteworthy here that average synset abstraction is no independent variable: due to the antisymmetry of the abstraction relation, certain synsets getting a lower-than-expected average abstraction value leads to other synsets getting a higher-than-expected average abstraction value. This might explain why synsets with more than one hundred occurrences on average have higher abstraction values.

Figure 7.1. Average synset abstraction level in comparison to synset occurrence count.

It may be the case that conceptors need a certain amount of synset exemplars before they can accurately describe the geometry of the synset, and to account for noise and outliers. Let us define a conceptor C 's quota $q : C_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ to map to the fraction of dimensions from the N -dimensional state space that is used by C [25]. It is equal to the conceptor's normalised trace, i.e. $q(C) = \text{trace}(C)/N$. For this hypothesis to be true, we may expect conceptor quota to scale linearly with occurrence as long as the occurrence threshold is not reached, and, as the conceptor is increasingly able to make succinct characterisations for the synsets' geometries, start growing sublinearly. It is expected that conceptor quota grows towards an asymptotic value that is (significantly) smaller than one; this is due to the fact that conceptors are built up from exemplars of the same synset, which are spatially separated from exemplar vectors of other synsets.

Figure 7.2 shows how the conceptor quota scales with synset occurrence count. In Figure 7.2a, we can see that conceptor quota remains within the same order of magnitude once a synset occurrence threshold is reached. In Figure 7.2b, we can see that conceptor quota scales linearly with occurrence count until that same threshold is reached. Such a linear scaling indicates that no dimensionality reduction has occurred; the conceptor at that point is a mere concatenation of the exemplar vectors. It is *overfitting* on these few exemplars. A conceptor created from $p < N$ exemplars will have at most p nonzero eigenvalues, but that does not mean that the synset encoded by these exemplars has at most p informative dimensions; there are just not enough data points to make an accurate estimation for the remaining dimensions in the BERT vector space. Future research may look into regularisation strategies to combat this kind of overfitting. An example is to introduce a regularising ridge on the correlation matrices from which to create conceptors. The correlation matrix can then be calculated as

$$R = \frac{1}{L}XX^T + \lambda I, \quad (7.1)$$

for some regularisation coefficient $\lambda \geq 0$.

The observations made above may explain why synsets with a low occurrence might be given a lower abstraction rating. However, the observed correlation may also be partly due to an inverse causality. Since abstract terms are more widely applicable, it may be expected that these occur more frequently in a corpus of natural text. For example, it may be expected that the

(a) Occurrence count normalised over N and conceptor quota, sorted on occurrence count. This plot shows how the two trends start to deviate from each other. (b) Conceptor quota in relation to synset occurrence count. The dotted curve shows the identity line.

Figure 7.2. Conceptor quota in comparison to normalised synset occurrence count.

synset [tree.n.01](#) in general occurs more often than the synset [coconut.n.03](#). In the BookCorpus, [tree.n.01](#) occurs 188 thousand times, whereas [coconut.n.03](#) occurs 165 times. Therefore, there is a higher probability that more concrete terms (which ideally would have a low estimated abstraction rating) occur less often than more abstract terms.

All these observations point towards a complex interplay of causalities, which makes it difficult to form one-dimensional conclusions. Future research could focus on extracting a single pair of correlating variables, to piecwisely unravel this interplay. For example, it might be possible to manually curate a dataset where every synset has the same amount of sentences. Furthermore, regularisation strategies may reduce the tendency of \succ to overfit. Nonetheless, these findings show the importance of a lower bound on exemplar occurrence count for abstraction estimations of high quality.

7.3 Hierarchies of Abstraction

In this section, abstraction graphs as per stage VI are constructed and interpreted. Firstly, since the Löwner ordering is a partial order and is therefore transitive, the fact that R_t too is transitive for any t and the fuzzy relation described by $\succ|_{\mathcal{E}}$ is (i.a.) max–min-transitive shows us that \succ might indeed be a sound estimator for Löwner order.

The complete graph \mathcal{G} is too large and too dense to be visually interpretable. To create an insightful visualisation of an extracted an abstraction graph we first limit ourselves to two small subset of synsets, namely:

(a) The transitive reduction of the thresholded graph of synset-set 1.

(b) The transitive reduction of the thresholded graph of synset-set 2.

Figure 7.3. Two subgraphs created from the large pairwise abstraction matrix.

Set 1: Flowers & trees

- [thing.n.04](#)
- [entity.n.01](#)
- [flower.n.01](#)
- [plant.n.02](#)
- [tree.n.01](#)
- [daffodil.n.01](#)

Set 2: Fruits & berries

- [thing.n.04](#)
- [entity.n.01](#)
- [fruit.n.01](#)
- [berry.n.01](#)
- [grape.n.01](#)
- [orange.n.01](#)
- [strawberry.n.01](#)

For both subsets, the thresholded graphs \mathcal{G}_t are constructed with a threshold value of $t = 0.1$. Given the observed transitivity of R_t , the *transitive reduction* [2] can be used for brevity, as it removes all transitive edges from the graph. The transitivity is still implied when we assume that the vertical position of all vertices corresponds with observed abstraction level. The reduced graphs can be seen in figures 7.3a and 7.3b.

Interpreting these graphs, we see a surprisingly accurate correspondence with intuitive abstraction. There are some observations that stand out, however. For instance, in the lower regions of both graphs we see some abstraction relations between terms that intuitively are not directly related at all. These are $\text{tree} \rightarrow \text{daffodil}$ and $\text{berry} \rightarrow \text{orange}$. The direct abstraction relation between fruit and strawberry should instead be a transitive relation that goes through berry. It appears that the system has classified fruit and berry as being unrelated in terms of abstraction: $\succ(\text{fruit}, \text{berry}) = 0.06$. This may be partly due to the fact that the set of sentences for berry also contains named entities and open compounds, as per the observations made

in Section 7.1. A similar observation can be made for the lack of abstraction between flower and plant as well as between tree and plant. Another possible reason for this is explored in Section 7.4.

The impact of the threshold parameter t

It may be pointed out that the chosen abstraction threshold t is of importance for the final abstraction hierarchy. In general, if a threshold is chosen that is very small, then the hierarchy that is returned will be one-dimensional chain of synsets from the most abstract to the most concrete term. Conversely, if the chosen threshold value is very large, then the returned hierarchy will have one, most abstract synset that is directly connected to some or all other synsets – up to the point that the synset abstraction graph becomes fully disconnected, when the chosen threshold is extremely high. This is due to the transitive reduction process, together with the fact that G_t is fully connected with $t = 0$ and becomes less and less densely connected as t grows towards 1. Intuitively, t can be seen as a desired *depth* (or, conversely, *shallowness*) parameter, where lower values for t lead to deeper graphs with more levels of abstraction, and higher levels for t lead to shallower graphs where fewer levels of abstraction.

Figure 7.4 shows an example of how t impacts abstraction graphs. The following synset subset is used:

- [thing.n.04](#);
- [fruit.n.01](#);
- [plant.n.02](#);
- [garden.n.01](#);
- [banana.n.02](#);
- [cabbage.n.01](#);
- [elm.n.01](#);
- [melon.n.01](#).

These synsets were chosen not only to intuitively span multiple levels of abstraction, but also to include some synsets where an abstraction relation might not be apparent intuitively. Moreover, all these synsets have more than 768 occurrences. In Figure 7.4a, the low threshold value $t = 0.02$ gives us a graph where almost all nodes have an in- and out-degree of one, except for the branching (and subsequent merging) of plant and fruit. Apparently the abstraction between these two synsets is smaller than 0.01; in fact, $\succ(\text{plant}, \text{fruit}) = 0.015$. Figures 7.4b and 7.4c show how direct links between synsets start appearing for larger values of t ; for instance, when $t = 0.1$, banana and cabbage are now directly connected to both plant and fruit. Similarly, garden is now a direct descendant of thing. Contrastingly, for $t = 0.08$ it is a descendant of plant. For Figure 7.4d, the threshold $t = 0.3$ is so large that most synsets are now direct descendants of thing, which is estimated as a very abstract term. Only melon is concrete enough to be connected to garden, fruit and plant instead of directly to thing.

The exact point at which the extraction threshold maximally aligns with intuition is still an open question and is impeded by the lack of a quantifiable evaluation metric for abstraction hierarchies. In addition, the term “intuition” is in itself ambiguous. For the graphs in Figure 7.4, one might argue that $t = 0.3$ might be a good fit, due to the fact that there are less connections between synsets that have no apparent abstraction rating. This comes at the cost however of

Figure 7.4. Abstraction graphs with four values for t .

Figure 7.5. Compact view of the transitive reduction of the complete graph \mathcal{G}_t with $t = 0$; synset index is omitted for brevity. *Top*: going from left to right, from the globally most abstract terms [topographic_point.n.01](#), [thing.n.03](#) and [thing.n.08](#), to the globally most concrete terms [radish_plant.n.01](#), [dogwood.n.02](#) and [avocado.n.02](#). *Bottom*: the same for all synsets with at least 768 (d_{BERT}) exemplar occurrences. The globally most abstract terms stay the same, whereas the globally most concrete terms are now [tulip.n.01](#), [coffee.n.02](#) and [semen.n.01](#).

apparently missing connections, for instance between banana and fruit. This point argues in favour of a lower threshold such as $t = 0.1$, or something in between these two values.

Let us now briefly look into abstraction ratings of the entire set of synsets. For this we can use the one dimensional graph that is created when taking $t = 0$. Figure 7.5 shows the first and last three nodes of this graph. The global root ([topographic_point.n.01](#)) and the global leaf ([avocado.n.02](#)) coincide with the globally most abstract and concrete terms, respectively. Note however that the topmost graph in this figure also includes synsets with low amounts of exemplar occurrences, which is the case for the three shown most concrete synsets. The lowermost graph shows the three most concrete terms when only looking at synsets for which there are at least 768 occurrences. This graph can be interpreted as a global weighted abstraction order of all extracted synsets. This order is given in full in Appendix C.3.

7.4 Abstraction Alignment

The project of this thesis was initiated with a definition for “abstraction” being equal to logical subsumption, i.e. word x is more abstract than word y if and only if the class of all x ’s subsumes the class of all y ’s, formally $X \supseteq Y$. However, the results from the developed pipeline seem to lay bare an interesting discrepancy between this logic-based interpretation of linguistic abstraction relations, and the more empirically developing statistical abstractions that are extracted from large bodies of text.

Let us take as example the synsets [plant.n.02](#) and [flower.n.01](#). Intuitively, the former is more abstract than the latter, as the former directly *subsumes* the latter, i.e. all flowers are plants. However, we find that $\succ(\text{plant}, \text{flower}) = 0.02$, indicating no apparent semantic relation in either direction.

An explanation for discrepancy with intuitive subsumption could be that, in the sentences of the present corpus, the word *plant* is never or not often used to refer to *flower*. According to Grice's Maxim of Quantity [17, 18], people make their discourse contributions *exactly* as informative as required, and thus not more informative than needed. The hypothesis is then that using *plant* to refer to *flower* is most often not informative enough. Flowers often have a significant role in discourse as compared to other plants, due to the significant emotional role that flowers have in human culture. For example, the sentence "I'll bring you some flowers" has an entirely different meaning than "I'll bring you some plants", and this difference is larger than the "thing that is brought". The former sentence implies some kind of special occasion – the one to bring someone flowers for. Additionally, the receiver's implied action is different – flowers would be put in a vase and displayed indoors, whereas plants would be planted in a garden or planter.

The result is then that people don't think of flowers when the word *plant* is used – if the author meant to refer to flowers, then they would have used *flower* instead. Another, perhaps more intuitive example of this phenomenon is the distinction between human and animal. Strictly speaking, all humans are animals, yet when the word *animal* is used in discourse, it is most often used to refer to all animals that are not humans.

Some other synsets for which this phenomenon might be present are:

- fruit.n.01 ~ berry.n.01** Intuition would dictate that *fruit* is a more abstract term than *berry*. We find however that $\succ(\text{fruit}, \text{berry}) = 0.06$. There are certain predispositions that come with berries, namely that they often come in relatively large amounts and can be eaten whole. It is therefore often relevant to refer to berries specifically; for instance, the connotation with a bowl of fruits as compared to a bowl of berries is totally different. It is also worth noting that there is a discrepancy between the formal, botanical definition of a berry (a fruit that grows from a single ovary) with the popular definition (a small, round and juicy fruit) that will intuitively be used in non-formal discourse. In the former definition, a banana is a berry (it is not often referred to as a berry), and in the latter, cherries and strawberries are berries (they are not, but are referred to as berries – what's in a name).
- berry.n.01 ~ grape.n.01** Officially (cf. the botanical definition above) a grape is a kind of berry. However, we find that $\succ(\text{berry}, \text{grape}) = 0.06$, leading to grape being directly connected to fruit in the graph of Figure 7.3b. This phenomenon might be due to the specific role that grapes have as compared to other berries. They have been cultivated from a very early age, and are also hold cultural significance through for instance their use in winemaking. This commonly sets grapes apart from other berries.
- organism.n.01 ~ plant.n.02** Technically all plants and animals (and thus humans) are organisms, yet we find that $\succ(\text{organism}, \text{plant}) = -0.13$. The word *organism* is not often used to refer to so large a group, discourse in academic biology being the notable exception. Additionally, *organism* can be used to solely refer to single-cell organisms, as there is no more specific term available that still encompasses all single-cell organisms.

The occurrence of this phenomenon might be related to a significant role that the concrete term plays in human discourse as compared to all other items that are part of the abstract term, or the niche environment in which the abstract term is used. Future research might be able to devise an experiment that attempts to expose such a phenomenon in human discourse production and consumption.

7.5 *Opening the World of Language*

Despite the size of the WordNet knowledge base, it is not inconceivable that there will be input target nouns that have senses that are not part of the word sense classification model’s vocabulary. This is especially true for an application domain as fluid and organic as language, since word meanings continually appear and change. This is only amplified due to increasing globalisation [8].

This might not be immediately apparent in a corpus like the BookCorpus, given that it consists only of books and thus primarily uses *administered language*, i.e. language that is consciously and deliberately learned and explicitly formulated [44]. Contrastingly, *unadministered language* is spontaneous and mostly oral language, continuously adapting to changing communication requirements [27]. The language that is used on informal social media platforms could be seen as a special written form of unadministered language — think for example of spontaneously emerging digital acronyms and slang such as “tl;dr”, “cuz”, “lll”, “noob”, “rofl”, and “prolly”.

The word sense classification stage of the current pipeline currently operates under the *closed-world assumption* [63], which is the assumption that the “classification world” is entirely and exhaustively defined by the training sense vocabulary. The sense classification stage employed in the pipeline acts as a clear-cut CWE-to-synset mapping function, and as such makes this assumption implicitly — the world is defined by the function’s codomain. It is unlikely that this has a direct impact on the results of the current thesis, given that all performed experiments stay within the closed world defined by the input set of target nouns. However, this is not necessarily the case when using corpora extracted from other outlets such as social media, or spoken conversations.

It might therefore be beneficial for the pipeline’s robustness to explicitly reject the closed-world assumption. Machine learning with the assumption that not all possible classes are available at training time is called *Open-World Machine Learning* (OWML). An excellent entry-point to this field can be found in Parmar et al. [59].

For example, it might be possible to extend the word sense classification stage with a notion of classification (un)certainity, on which it is then possible to qualify or filter synset entries. This can be done either by extracting the probabilities from the final softmax layer (where an increasingly uniform output distribution indicates an uncertain or low quality classification), or by re-training the entire model with an additional “don’t know/unseen” output class.

Another option would be to extend the lexical knowledge base that is used by the classification model to account for an open world. It might be possible to attempt graph completion — estimating the probability of missing links between entities — on the WordNet LKB under the open-world assumption, i.e. assume that there may be new unseen entities. An example for such an open-world graph completion algorithm is detailed in Shi and Weninger [68].

Finally, it may be possible for the purpose of simply clustering polysemous word clouds into single-meaning word sense clouds to move to fully unsupervised word sense disambiguation. The exact meaning attached to a cluster is not relevant, when the goal is to simply estimate abstraction relations between monosemous clusters. This would make the closed-world principle irrelevant, as there is no vocabulary of output classes to make assumptions about. Future research may look into how to use EWISER’s CWE sense space projections directly for this purpose, instead of comparing these to the vocabulary of sense recipe vectors as it is done in the current implementation.

8 Conclusion

8.1 Answering the Research Questions

Let us recite the main [research question](#) posed in the introduction:

Can the abstraction hierarchy between word lemmata be recovered using conceptors of contextual embedding clouds? What are the difficulties?

In this section, we attempt to answer this question by means of answering the sub-questions that were introduced in [Chapter 1](#) as well. Additionally, points of future research are listed when relevant. The sub-questions are discussed in order in the sections that follow:

i. How can clouds of polysemous word embeddings be split into clouds of monosemous lemmata?

A state-of-the-art word sense disambiguation pipeline can be used as preprocessing step in the pipeline for extracting abstraction hierarchies. However, it does not create a partition of polysemous word clouds into monosemous word clouds; instead, due to word synonymy, the vector clouds of all words together are reordered into sense vector clouds, each consisting of a set of synonym words (synsets).

Some linguistic constructs, such as named entities, compound words and metonyms, may not be correctly interpreted by the current pipeline, which means that their senses may not be effectively disambiguated. Moreover, the closed-world assumption under which this stage of the pipeline operates may not be suitable for semantic analysis of language. Future research might look into how to extend the vectorisation and WSD methods to alleviate these issues. Some pointers are given in [Section 7.1](#).

ii. How can conceptors be used to estimate the abstraction relation between two conceptors?

The Löwner order provides conceptors with an analog for concept-to-concept abstraction. A heuristic that focuses on the magnitude of eigenvalues of the difference matrix seems to effectively capture this property and may act as a graded variant of the Löwner order. Moreover, the heuristic is able to maintain the Löwner order's transitivity property, when this property is extended to fuzzy relations.

Despite ignoring null eigenvalues in the aforementioned heuristic, there is still a significant correlation between occurrence count and average synset abstraction. The heuristic is still prone to overfitting. Evaluating conceptor quota in relation to occurrence count showed that, in the current experiments, a certain constant amount of occurrences were needed before conceptors were able to make a proper characterisation of the synsets' geometry. Future research could look into extracting rules or insightful metrics on minimum exemplar occurrence count that ensures a good conceptor characterisation of the exemplar vector cloud, as well as applying regularisation strategies to the heuristic.

iii. How can these binary abstraction relations be aggregated into hierarchies of abstractions?

The abstraction matrix that is created by performing a pairwise synset comparison with the Löwner heuristic, can be immediately and interpreted without loss of information as a weighted and directed graph. This graph is suitable for use as a knowledge base and for graph processing algorithms directly, but it is not fit for human interpretation due to its density. It is possible to create interpretable graphs by taking the transitive reduction of a thresholded variant of a subgraph from the “master”-graph. This is a destructive process, and choosing the optimal threshold value is nontrivial and might ultimately depend on the chosen datasets, and embedding and WSD methods.

iv. To what extent do the estimated abstraction hierarchies correspond with both the formally defined subsumption model and intuitive human estimations for abstraction hierarchies?

The developed abstraction relation is transitive, and as such aligns with the logical subsumption model. However, manual inspection of estimated abstraction values of certain synsets showed that it does not always align with logical subsumption. Explaining these observations requires extensive research in discourse theory in combination with lexical semantics and cultural considerations. Some preliminary reasoning was attempted with respect of common discourse maxims in Section 7.4, but this is seen as a mere stepping stone towards a plethora of research directions.

8.2 General Conclusion

Stepping back, it seems that the conceptor-based method for extracting abstraction hierarchies has some potential. We do see however that individual parts of the developed pipeline can be refined further to improve general accuracy. Additionally, the misalignment of the extracted hierarchies to logical subsumption opens up discussions not only on the efficacy of the present pipeline, but also on how humans internally represent word-to-word abstraction. The latter point can however not be explored without strings attached until the former point is adequately resolved – the observed misalignment may still be partly due to implementational deficiencies and overfitting.

The general contribution of this thesis is twofold. Firstly, the research in the mechanism of conceptors, and combining it with large language models such as BERT, contributes to the area of neuro-symbolic integration: the integration of data-intensive and sub-symbolic neural networks with a mechanism that allows for symbolic reasoning. Secondly, the findings in formal–human abstraction misalignment may add to the understanding of how humans interpret and use concept-to-concept abstraction in discourse and cognition.

BACK MATTER

A *Final Words*

A.1 *Acknowledgements*

The research for and the writing of this thesis has felt like taking a stroll on a mine-field of rabbit holes; the art has lied in deciding in which rabbit holes to allow yourself to fall – and at what point to start climbing back out again. I would primarily like to thank my supervisor, Herbert Jaeger, for shielding off some rabbit holes *a priori* and providing me with guidance whenever I needed it. His enthusiasm for the field is infectious, which has boosted my motivation across the board.

Furthermore, I would like to thank my friends and family for always believing in me even when I did not, and for providing incidental but necessary distraction.

A.2 *Responsible Use of Generative AI*

Due to the explosive developments of generative AI, their current wide availability and the debate around their use especially in an educative setting, I found it most ethical to explicitly state how generative AI has and has not been used in the development of this thesis. This is particularly relevant for written works such as the present work, for it has become trivial to generate complete essays, sound save minor tweaks, within minutes. I therefore provide the following two lists:

For this thesis, generative AI was used to:

1. Provide pointers for acquiring new information;
2. Reformulate or summarise existing information;
3. Provide stylistic directions for existing text, without aiming to imitate a specific author;
4. Add documentation to existing blocks of code;
5. Aid in debugging existing faulty blocks of code.

Generative AI was *not* used to:

1. Acquire new knowledge, without properly checking cited sources manually;
2. Write or rewrite (parts of) paragraphs wholesale;
3. Implement or rewrite (parts of) the accompanying software suite wholesale;
4. Create (parts of) graphs and visualisations;
5. Imitate (a mix of) specific artists or authors.

I hope this addition will encourage others to adopt a similar explicit statement in their own works, and instigate ethical use of these valuable but notorious tools.

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C *Appendices*

C.1 *The Original Noun Set*

The following nouns were included in the original set of target nouns:

- | | | | |
|-------------------|--------------------|--------------------|-------------------|
| 1. agriculture | 33. farm | 65. maple | 97. salad |
| 2. algae | 34. fig | 66. meadow | 98. scent |
| 3. ancestry | 35. fig_tree | 67. melon | 99. seed |
| 4. apple | 36. flower | 68. monstrosity | 100. seedpod |
| 5. apple_tree | 37. foliage | 69. moss | 101. sheaf |
| 6. area | 38. forest | 70. myrtle | 102. shrub |
| 7. ash | 39. fruit | 71. nectar | 103. shrubbery |
| 8. avocado | 40. fruit_tree | 72. oleander | 104. sour |
| 9. banana | 41. garden | 73. orange | 105. spice |
| 10. bean | 42. grape | 74. organism | 106. strawberry |
| 11. beech | 43. grass | 75. palm | 107. sugar |
| 12. berry | 44. green | 76. pasture | 108. sweet |
| 13. blackberry | 45. greenhouse | 77. pea | 109. sweet_clover |
| 14. blight | 46. greens | 78. pear | 110. tending |
| 15. blossom | 47. growth | 79. peony | 111. thing |
| 16. branch | 48. hay | 80. pepper | 112. timber |
| 17. bud | 49. herb | 81. perfume | 113. tobacco |
| 18. cabbage | 50. honeysuckle | 82. petal | 114. tomato |
| 19. chrysanthemum | 51. horse_chestnut | 83. pine | 115. tree |
| 20. citron | 52. hyacinth | 84. place | 116. trunk |
| 21. coco_palm | 53. jam | 85. plaintain_lily | 117. tulip |
| 22. coconut | 54. jelly | 86. plant | 118. turf |
| 23. coffee | 55. jonquil | 87. planting | 119. vegetable |
| 24. corn | 56. landscape | 88. plowing | 120. verbena |
| 25. country | 57. larkspur | 89. poppy | 121. violet |
| 26. country | 58. lawn | 90. radish | 122. vitamin |
| 27. daffodil | 59. leaf | 91. rhubarb | 123. wallflower |
| 28. daisy | 60. lemon | 92. rocket | 124. weed |
| 29. dogwood | 61. lemon_tree | 93. root | 125. weeds |
| 30. eggplant | 62. lilac | 94. rose | 126. willow |
| 31. elm | 63. lime_tree | 95. rot | 127. wood |
| 32. entity | 64. living_thing | 96. sage | 128. yellow_pine |

C.2 Glossary of Extracted Synsets

The table that is shown below contains the set of synsets that was extracted from the original set of target nouns by the WSD framework. The entries in the “Synset” column link to the respective pages in the online [WordNet Navigator](#). For readers on print, one can create a direct link to the correct word search by appending the synset name without the .n.XX suffix to the following url:

<http://wordnetweb.princeton.edu/perl/webwn?c=7&s=>

For example, the WordNet link to [alga.n.01](#) is <http://wordnetweb.princeton.edu/perl/webwn?c=7&s=alga>.

Synset	Count	Gloss
alga.n.01	557	primitive chlorophyll-containing mainly aquatic eukaryotic organisms lacking true stems and roots and leaves
ambrosia.n.04	3	(classical mythology) the food and drink of the gods; mortals who ate it became immortal
ancestor.n.01	327	someone from whom you are descended (but usually more remote than a grandparent)
ancestry.n.02	636	inherited properties shared with others of your bloodline
agribusiness.n.01	148	a large-scale farming enterprise
apple.n.01	19,371	fruit with red or yellow or green skin and sweet to tart crisp whitish flesh
apple.n.02	276	native Eurasian tree widely cultivated in many varieties for its firm rounded edible fruits
area.n.01	61,485	a particular geographical region of indefinite boundary (usually serving some special purpose or distinguished by its people or culture or geography)
area.n.02	4,258	a subject of study
area.n.03	6,342	a part of an animal that has a special function or is supplied by a given artery or nerve
area.n.05	36,100	a part of a structure having some specific characteristic or function
area.n.06	5,378	the extent of a 2-dimensional surface enclosed within a boundary
arm.n.02	49	any projection that is thought to resemble a human arm
aroma.n.02	48,139	a distinctive odor that is pleasant
ash.n.01	15,959	the residue that remains when something is burned
ash.n.02	2,403	any of various deciduous pinnate-leaved ornamental or timber trees of the genus <i>Fraxinus</i>
ash.n.03	2	strong elastic wood of any of various ash trees; used for furniture and tool handles and sporting goods such as baseball bats
attic.n.03	65	informal terms for a human head
avocado.n.01	536	a pear-shaped tropical fruit with green or blackish skin and rich yellowish pulp enclosing a single large seed
avocado.n.02	1	tropical American tree bearing large pulpy green fruits
banana.n.01	288	any of several tropical and subtropical treelike herbs of the genus <i>Musa</i> having a terminal crown of large entire leaves and usually bearing hanging clusters of elongated fruits
banana.n.02	3,973	elongated crescent-shaped yellow fruit with soft sweet flesh
bean.n.01	4,910	any of various edible seeds of plants of the family Leguminosae used for food

Synset	Count	Gloss
bean.n.02	3,399	any of various seeds or fruits that are beans or resemble beans
bean.n.03	494	any of various leguminous plants grown for their edible seeds and pods
beech.n.01	264	any of several large deciduous trees with rounded spreading crowns and smooth grey bark and small sweet edible triangular nuts enclosed in burs; north temperate regions
beginning.n.04	3,375	the place where something begins, where it springs into being
berry.n.01	3,895	any of numerous small and pulpy edible fruits; used as desserts or in making jams and jellies and preserves
berry.n.02	445	a small fruit having any of various structures, e.g., simple (grape or blueberry) or aggregate (blackberry or raspberry)
blackberry.n.01	2,639	large sweet black or very dark purple edible aggregate fruit of any of various bushes of the genus <i>Rubus</i>
blackberry.n.02	4	bramble with sweet edible black or dark purple berries that usually do not separate from the receptacle
blight.n.01	667	a state or condition being blighted
blight.n.02	75	any plant disease resulting in withering without rotting
blush_wine.n.01	2	pinkish table wine from red grapes whose skins were removed after fermentation began
boodle.n.01	66	informal terms for money
branch.n.01	3,897	a division of some larger or more complex organization
branch.n.02	34,432	a division of a stem, or secondary stem arising from the main stem of a plant
branch.n.03	493	a part of a forked or branching shape
branch.n.05	138	a stream or river connected to a larger one
bud.n.01	3,605	a partially opened flower
bud.n.02	3,208	a swelling on a plant stem consisting of overlapping immature leaves or petals
bundle.n.02	1,337	a package of several things tied together for carrying or storing
bunk.n.04	2	unacceptable behavior (especially ludicrously false statements)
cabbage.n.01	1,400	any of various types of cabbage
cabbage.n.03	1	any of various cultivars of the genus <i>Brassica oleracea</i> grown for their edible leaves or flowers
capsicum.n.01	321	any of various tropical plants of the genus <i>Capsicum</i> bearing peppers
carbohydrate.n.01	402	an essential structural component of living cells and source of energy for animals; includes simple sugars with small molecules as well as macromolecular substances; are classified according to the number of monosaccharide groups they contain
care.n.01	42	the work of providing treatment for or attending to someone or something
chocolate.n.03	35	a medium brown to dark-brown color
chrysanthemum.n.01	146	the flower of a chrysanthemum plant
chrysanthemum.n.02	2	any of numerous perennial Old World herbs having showy brightly colored flower heads of the genera <i>Chrysanthemum</i> , <i>Argyranthemum</i> , <i>Dendranthema</i> , <i>Tanacetum</i> ; widely cultivated
citron.n.01	65	large lemonlike fruit with thick aromatic rind; usually preserved
coconut.n.01	1,469	the edible white meat of a coconut; often shredded for use in e.g. cakes and curries
coconut.n.02	287	large hard-shelled oval nut with a fibrous husk containing thick white meat surrounding a central cavity filled (when fresh) with fluid or milk

Synset	Count	Gloss
coconut.n.03	181	tall palm tree bearing coconuts as fruits; widely planted throughout the tropics
coffee_bean.n.01	20	a seed of the coffee tree; ground to make coffee
coffee.n.01	118,964	a beverage consisting of an infusion of ground coffee beans
coffee.n.02	1,490	any of several small trees and shrubs native to the tropical Old World yielding coffee beans
corn_whiskey.n.01	1	whiskey distilled from a mash of not less than 80 percent corn
corn.n.01	3,998	tall annual cereal grass bearing kernels on large ears: widely cultivated in America in many varieties; the principal cereal in Mexico and Central and South America since pre-Columbian times
corn.n.02	361	the dried grains or kernels or corn used as animal feed or ground for meal
corn.n.03	1,451	ears of corn that can be prepared and served for human food
corn.n.07	1	something sentimental or trite
country.n.02	30,282	the territory occupied by a nation
country.n.04	17,342	an area outside of cities and towns
crush.n.02	264	a dense crowd of people
daffodil.n.01	563	any of numerous varieties of Narcissus plants having showy often yellow flowers with a trumpet-shaped central crown
daisy.n.01	11,761	any of numerous composite plants having flower heads with well-developed ray flowers usually arranged in a single whorl
decomposition.n.04	624	(biology) the process of decay caused by bacterial or fungal action
decoration.n.02	1	an award for winning a championship or commemorating some other event
department_of_agriculture.n.01	1	the federal department that administers programs that provide services to farmers (including research and soil conservation and efforts to stabilize the farming economy); created in 1862
dessert.n.01	65	a dish served as the last course of a meal
dogwood.n.01	214	a tree or shrub of the genus Cornus often having showy bracts resembling flowers
dogwood.n.02	1	hard tough wood of any dogwood of the genus Cornus; resembles boxwood
eatage.n.01	33	bulky food like grass or hay for browsing or grazing horses or cattle
eggplant.n.01	165	egg-shaped vegetable having a shiny skin typically dark purple but occasionally white or yellow
eggplant.n.02	5	hairy upright herb native to southeastern Asia but widely cultivated for its large glossy edible fruit commonly used as a vegetable
elm.n.01	1,071	any of various trees of the genus Ulmus: important timber or shade trees
elm.n.02	32	hard tough wood of an elm tree; used for e.g. implements and furniture
emergence.n.01	1	the gradual beginning or coming forth
entity.n.01	5,184	that which is perceived or known or inferred to have its own distinct existence (living or nonliving)
etymon.n.01	1	a simple form inferred as the common basis from which related words in several languages can be derived by linguistic processes
farm.n.01	25,116	workplace consisting of farm buildings and cultivated land as a unit
farming.n.01	324	the practice of cultivating the land or raising stock
fig.n.02	575	Mediterranean tree widely cultivated for its edible fruit
fig.n.04	410	fleshy sweet pear-shaped yellowish or purple multiple fruit eaten fresh or preserved or dried
figure.n.01	2	a diagram or picture illustrating textual material

Synset	Count	Gloss
fix.n.01	797	informal terms for a difficult situation
flower.n.01	35,937	a plant cultivated for its blooms or blossoms
flower.n.02	20,479	reproductive organ of angiosperm plants especially one having showy or colorful parts
flower.n.03	403	the period of greatest prosperity or productivity
foliation.n.03	2	(architecture) leaf-like architectural ornament
forest.n.01	65,612	the trees and other plants in a large densely wooded area
forest.n.02	6,644	land that is covered with trees and shrubs
freak.n.01	992	a person or animal that is markedly unusual or deformed
fruit.n.01	19,021	the ripened reproductive body of a seed plant
fruit.n.03	483	the consequence of some effort or action
gamboge.n.02	347	a strong yellow color
garden.n.01	34,725	a plot of ground where plants are cultivated
garden.n.02	1,078	the flowers or vegetables or fruits or herbs that are cultivated in a garden
garden.n.03	8,040	a yard or lawn adjoining a house
gelatin.n.02	396	an edible jelly (sweet or pungent) made with gelatin and used as a dessert or salad base or a coating for foods
grape.n.01	4,452	any of various juicy fruit of the genus <i>Vitis</i> with green or purple skins; grow in clusters
grape.n.02	32	any of numerous woody vines of genus <i>Vitis</i> bearing clusters of edible berries
grapeshot.n.01	3	a cluster of small projectiles fired together from a cannon to produce a hail of shot
grass.n.01	50,072	narrow-leaved green herbage: grown as lawns; used as pasture for grazing animals; cut and dried as hay
grass.n.02	1	German writer of novels and poetry and plays (born 1927)
green.n.01	10,149	green color or pigment; resembling the color of growing grass
green.n.03	4	United States labor leader who was president of the American Federation of Labor from 1924 to 1952 and who led the struggle with the Congress of Industrial Organizations (1873-1952)
green.n.04	6	an environmentalist who belongs to the Green Party
green.n.06	870	an area of closely cropped grass surrounding the hole on a golf course
greenhouse.n.01	1,818	a building with glass walls and roof; for the cultivation and exhibition of plants under controlled conditions
greens.n.01	619	any of various leafy plants or their leaves and stems eaten as vegetables
growth.n.01	2,236	(biology) the process of an individual organism growing organically; a purely biological unfolding of events involved in an organism changing gradually from a simple to a more complex level
growth.n.02	1,051	a progression from simpler to more complex forms
growth.n.04	1,497	vegetation that has grown
growth.n.06	65	(pathology) an abnormal proliferation of tissue (as in a tumor)
growth.n.07	694	something grown or growing
hay.n.01	5,693	grass mowed and cured for use as fodder
hayfield.n.01	8,351	a field where grass or alfalfa are grown to be made into hay
herb.n.01	1,997	a plant lacking a permanent woody stem; many are flowering garden plants or potherbs; some having medicinal properties; some are pests
herb.n.02	5,500	aromatic potherb used in cookery for its savory qualities
home.n.01	38,745	where you live at a particular time
honeysuckle.n.01	1,113	shrub or vine of the genus <i>Lonicera</i>
hyacinth.n.01	12	a red transparent variety of zircon used as a gemstone

Synset	Count	Gloss
hyacinth.n.02	105	any of numerous bulbous perennial herbs
increase.n.03	526	a process of becoming larger or longer or more numerous or more important
jam.n.01	2,568	preserve of crushed fruit
jamming.n.01	252	deliberate radiation or reflection of electromagnetic energy for the purpose of disrupting enemy use of electronic devices or systems
jelly.n.02	157	a preserve made of the jelled juice of fruit
jelly.n.03	64	any substance having the consistency of jelly or gelatin
landscape.n.01	11,700	an expanse of scenery that can be seen in a single view
landscape.n.02	720	painting depicting an expanse of natural scenery
landscape.n.03	127	a genre of art dealing with the depiction of natural scenery
landscape.n.04	383	an extensive mental viewpoint
larkspur.n.01	5	any of numerous cultivated plants of the genus <i>Delphinium</i>
lawn.n.01	18,517	a field of cultivated and mowed grass
leaf.n.01	10,269	the main organ of photosynthesis and transpiration in higher plants
leaf.n.02	587	a sheet of any written or printed material (especially in a manuscript or book)
leaf.n.03	13	hinged or detachable flat section (as of a table or door)
lemon.n.01	4,040	yellow oval fruit with juicy acidic flesh
lemon.n.03	234	a small evergreen tree that originated in Asia but is widely cultivated for its fruit
lemon.n.04	752	a distinctive tart flavor characteristic of lemons
lemon.n.05	6	an artifact (especially an automobile) that is defective or unsatisfactory
lilac.n.01	468	any of various plants of the genus <i>Syringa</i> having large panicles of usually fragrant flowers
lineage.n.01	214	the descendants of one individual
luggage_compartment.n.01	6,914	compartment in an automobile that carries luggage or shopping or tools
lumber.n.01	1,258	the wood of trees cut and prepared for use as building material
maple.n.01	2,517	wood of any of various maple trees; especially the hard close-grained wood of the sugar maple; used especially for furniture and flooring
maple.n.02	335	any of numerous trees or shrubs of the genus <i>Acer</i> bearing winged seeds in pairs; north temperate zone
matter.n.01	44,124	a vaguely specified concern
melon.n.01	1,312	any of numerous fruits of the gourd family having a hard rind and sweet juicy flesh
melon.n.02	3	any of various fruit of cucurbitaceous vines including: muskmelons; watermelons; cantaloupes; cucumbers
monstrosity.n.02	961	something hideous or frightful
moss.n.01	4,457	tiny leafy-stemmed flowerless plants
myrtle.n.01	1,293	widely cultivated as a groundcover for its dark green shiny leaves and usually blue-violet flowers
myrtle.n.02	48	any evergreen shrub or tree of the genus <i>Myrtus</i>
nation.n.02	1,746	the people who live in a nation or country
nectar.n.01	1,063	a sweet liquid secretion that is attractive to pollinators
nectar.n.02	1	fruit juice especially when undiluted
oleander.n.01	178	an ornamental but poisonous flowering shrub having narrow evergreen leaves and clusters of fragrant white to pink or red flowers: native to East Indies but widely cultivated in warm regions
olfactory_property.n.01	2,410	any property detected by the olfactory system
orange.n.01	4,351	round yellow to orange fruit of any of several citrus trees

Synset	Count	Gloss
orange.n.02	8,358	orange color or pigment; any of a range of colors between red and yellow
orange.n.03	263	any citrus tree bearing oranges
orange.n.04	10	any pigment producing the orange color
organism.n.01	1,861	a living thing that has (or can develop) the ability to act or function independently
organism.n.02	15	a system considered analogous in structure or function to a living body
outgrowth.n.01	99	a natural consequence of development
palm.n.01	81,503	the inner surface of the hand from the wrist to the base of the fingers
palm.n.02	19	a linear unit based on the length or width of the human hand
palm.n.03	5,949	any plant of the family Palmae having an unbranched trunk crowned by large pinnate or palmate leaves
park.n.02	904	a piece of open land for recreational use in an urban area
pasture.n.01	3,496	a field covered with grass or herbage and suitable for grazing by livestock
pea.n.01	3,984	seed of a pea plant used for food
pea.n.02	7	the fruit or seed of a pea plant
pea.n.03	98	a leguminous plant of the genus <i>Pisum</i> with small white flowers and long green pods containing edible green seeds
pear.n.01	950	sweet juicy gritty-textured fruit available in many varieties
pear.n.02	10	Old World tree having sweet gritty-textured juicy fruit; widely cultivated in many varieties
peony.n.01	214	any of numerous plants widely cultivated for their showy single or double red or pink or white flowers
pepper.n.01	78	climber having dark red berries (peppercorns) when fully ripe; southern India and Sri Lanka; naturalized in northern Burma and Assam
pepper.n.03	4,273	pungent seasoning from the berry of the common pepper plant of East India; use whole or ground
pepper.n.04	766	sweet and hot varieties of fruits of plants of the genus <i>Capsicum</i>
perfume.n.02	3,203	a toiletry that emits and diffuses a fragrant odor
petal.n.01	5,599	part of the perianth that is usually brightly colored
pieplant.n.01	84	long pinkish sour leafstalks usually eaten cooked and sweetened
pine.n.01	8,873	a coniferous tree
pine.n.02	1,597	straight-grained durable and often resinous white to yellowish timber of any of numerous trees of the genus <i>Pinus</i>
place.n.02	73,190	any area set aside for a particular purpose
place.n.03	23,163	an abstract mental location
place.n.04	24,887	a general vicinity
place.n.06	5,178	a particular situation
place.n.10	2,270	proper or designated social situation
place.n.12	1,166	the passage that is being read
place.n.13	1,741	proper or appropriate position or location
place.n.15	14,478	an item on a list or in a sequence
plant.n.01	4,964	buildings for carrying on industrial labor
plant.n.02	19,786	(botany) a living organism lacking the power of locomotion
plant.n.03	1	an actor situated in the audience whose acting is rehearsed but seems spontaneous to the audience
plant.n.04	205	something planted secretly for discovery by another
planting.n.01	265	the act of fixing firmly in place
planting.n.02	20	a collection of plants (trees or shrubs or flowers) in a particular area
planting.n.03	681	putting seeds or young plants in the ground to grow

Synset	Count	Gloss
plaza.n.01	2	a public square with room for pedestrians
plowing.n.01	43	tilling the land with a plow
pod.n.02	4	a several-seeded dehiscent fruit as e.g. of a leguminous plant
poppy.n.01	395	annual or biennial or perennial herbs having showy flowers
position.n.01	17,266	the particular portion of space occupied by something
position.n.06	1,123	a job in an organization
pot.n.09	2,021	street names for marijuana
proboscis.n.02	501	a long flexible snout as of an elephant
putrefaction.n.01	609	a state of decay usually accompanied by an offensive odor
radish_plant.n.01	1	a cruciferous plant of the genus <i>Raphanus</i> having a pungent edible root
radish.n.01	137	pungent fleshy edible root
rocket.n.01	4,942	any vehicle self-propelled by a rocket engine
rocket.n.02	47	a jet engine containing its own propellant and driven by reaction propulsion
rocket.n.03	1	erect European annual often grown as a salad crop to be harvested when young and tender
rocket.n.04	31	propels bright light high in the sky, or used to propel a lifesaving line or harpoon
root.n.01	13,795	(botany) the usually underground organ that lacks buds or leaves or nodes; absorbs water and mineral salts; usually it anchors the plant to the ground
root.n.03	155	(linguistics) the form of a word after all affixes are removed
root.n.04	45	a number that, when multiplied by itself some number of times, equals a given number
root.n.08	744	the part of a tooth that is embedded in the jaw and serves as support
rose.n.01	18,479	any of many shrubs of the genus <i>Rosa</i> that bear roses
rose.n.03	954	a dusty pink color
sage.n.01	4,274	a mentor in spiritual and philosophical topics who is renowned for profound wisdom
sage.n.02	1,106	aromatic fresh or dried grey-green leaves used widely as seasoning for meats and fowl and game etc
sage.n.03	1,382	any of various plants of the genus <i>Salvia</i> ; a cosmopolitan herb
salad.n.01	7,640	food mixtures either arranged on a plate or tossed and served with a moist dressing; usually consisting of or including greens
scent.n.02	28,839	an odor left in passing by which a person or animal can be traced
seat.n.01	5,124	a space reserved for sitting (as in a theater or on a train or airplane)
seed.n.01	3,310	a small hard fruit
seed.n.02	5,077	a mature fertilized plant ovule consisting of an embryo and its food source and having a protective coat or testa
seeded_player.n.01	42	one of the outstanding players in a tournament
semen.n.01	2,108	the thick white fluid containing spermatozoa that is ejaculated by the male genital tract
shrub.n.01	2,952	a low woody perennial plant usually having several major stems
shrubbery.n.01	335	an area where a number of shrubs are planted
shrubbery.n.02	763	a collection of shrubs growing together
skyrocket.n.02	32	sends a firework display high into the sky
solution.n.04	18	the set of values that give a true statement when substituted into an equation
source.n.03	1,373	anything that provides inspiration for later work
space.n.07	58	a blank area
sphere.n.01	814	a particular environment or walk of life

Synset	Count	Gloss
spice.n.01	2,419	aromatic substances of vegetable origin used as a preservative
spice.n.02	1,328	any of a variety of pungent aromatic vegetable substances used for flavoring food
spiciness.n.01	1,223	the property of being seasoned with spice and so highly flavored
state.n.04	11,919	a politically organized body of people under a single government
stead.n.01	21,853	the post or function properly or customarily occupied or served by another
strawberry.n.01	6,094	sweet fleshy red fruit
strawberry.n.03	1	a soft red birthmark
sugar.n.01	17,717	a white crystalline carbohydrate used as a sweetener and preservative
supergrass.n.01	1	a police informer who implicates many people
sweet.n.03	1,962	a food rich in sugar
sweet.n.04	22	the taste experience when sugar dissolves in the mouth
thing.n.01	95,120	a special situation
thing.n.02	111,474	an action
thing.n.03	29,521	a special abstraction
thing.n.04	52,859	an artifact
thing.n.05	57,569	an event
thing.n.07	56,459	a statement regarded as an object
thing.n.08	62,633	an entity that is not named specifically
thing.n.09	50,847	any attribute or quality considered as having its own existence
thing.n.10	5,006	a special objective
thing.n.11	3,279	a persistent illogical feeling of desire or aversion
thing.n.12	2	a separate and self-contained entity
timber.n.02	1,522	a beam made of wood
timber.n.03	724	a post made of wood
timbre.n.01	44	(music) the distinctive property of a complex sound (a voice or noise or musical sound)
tobacco.n.01	4,210	leaves of the tobacco plant dried and prepared for smoking or ingestion
tobacco.n.02	47	aromatic annual or perennial herbs and shrubs
tomato.n.01	4,966	mildly acid red or yellow pulpy fruit eaten as a vegetable
tomato.n.02	8	native to South America; widely cultivated in many varieties
topographic_point.n.01	265,819	a point located with respect to surface features of some region
torso.n.01	545	the body excluding the head and neck and limbs
tree.n.01	188,636	a tall perennial woody plant having a main trunk and branches forming a distinct elevated crown; includes both gymnosperms and angiosperms
tree.n.02	1,345	a figure that branches from a single root
tree.n.03	3	English actor and theatrical producer noted for his lavish productions of Shakespeare (1853-1917)
trunk.n.01	12,477	the main stem of a tree; usually covered with bark; the bole is usually the part that is commercially useful for lumber
trunk.n.02	7,589	luggage consisting of a large strong case used when traveling or for storage
tulip.n.01	1,046	any of numerous perennial bulbous herbs having linear or broadly lanceolate leaves and usually a single showy flower
turf.n.01	1,222	surface layer of ground containing a mat of grass and grass roots
turf.n.02	800	the territory claimed by a juvenile gang as its own
turf.n.03	243	range of jurisdiction or influence
vegetable.n.01	8,835	edible seeds or roots or stems or leaves or bulbs or tubers or nonsweet fruits of any of numerous herbaceous plant

Synset	Count	Gloss
vegetable.n.02	3	any of various herbaceous plants cultivated for an edible part such as the fruit or the root of the beet or the leaf of spinach or the seeds of bean plants or the flower buds of broccoli or cauliflower
verbena.n.01	373	any of numerous tropical or subtropical American plants of the genus <i>Verbena</i> grown for their showy spikes of variously colored flowers
violet.n.01	1,506	any of numerous low-growing violas with small flowers
violet.n.02	15,632	a variable color that lies beyond blue in the spectrum
vitamin.n.01	1,776	any of a group of organic substances essential in small quantities to normal metabolism
wallflower.n.01	35	any of numerous plants of the genus <i>Erysimum</i> having fragrant yellow or orange or brownish flowers
wallflower.n.03	186	remains on sidelines at social event
weed.n.01	7,573	any plant that crowds out cultivated plants
weed.n.02	14	a black band worn by a man (on the arm or hat) as a sign of mourning
willow.n.01	6,845	any of numerous deciduous trees and shrubs of the genus <i>Salix</i>
willow.n.02	1	a textile machine having a system of revolving spikes for opening and cleaning raw textile fibers
wood.n.01	52,795	the hard fibrous lignified substance under the bark of trees
wood.n.03	2	United States film actress (1938-1981)
wood.n.04	5	English conductor (1869-1944)
wood.n.05	15	English writer of novels about murders and thefts and forgeries (1814-1887)
wood.n.06	1	United States painter noted for works based on life in the Midwest (1892-1942)
wood.n.08	136	a golf club with a long shaft used to hit long shots; originally made with a wooden head
woodwind.n.01	1	any wind instrument other than the brass instruments
yield.n.03	333	an amount of a product

C.3 Global Abstraction Ordering

The table that is shown below contains the global abstraction ordering of the extracted synsets. Any row containing a synset with less than $d_{\text{BERT}} = 768$ occurrences has been italicised. The “Abstraction” column indicates the estimated abstraction value $\succ(\text{previous}, \text{current})$ between that synset and the previous synset. The intensity of the colouring of its cells corresponds with the magnitude of the abstraction. This acts as a visual aid to discriminate synset pairs with bigger abstraction gaps. The “Cumulative” column contains the cumulative sum of the aforementioned abstraction rating. “Count” indicates synset occurrence count. The first entry is the globally most abstract synset, whereas the final entry is the globally most concrete synset.

№	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
0	topographic_point.1	N/A	0	163,845
1	thing.3	0.06813	0.07	18,050
2	thing.8	0.03813	0.11	37,871
3	place.3	0.00769	0.11	14,553
4	thing.5	0.00071	0.11	34,690
5	thing.1	0.00306	0.12	55,558
6	matter.1	0.08262	0.2	26,278
7	stead.1	0.01453	0.21	13,719
8	thing.4	0.03174	0.25	32,710
9	thing.2	0.00169	0.25	66,373
10	position.1	0.00692	0.26	11,127
11	thing.9	0.00564	0.26	30,267
12	thing.7	0.00862	0.27	32,378
13	branch.1	0.01273	0.28	2,674
14	root.1	0.03011	0.31	9,010
15	area.6	0.01202	0.32	3,643
16	beginning.4	0.00164	0.33	2,244
17	place.6	0.03154	0.36	3,227
18	green.1	0.00460	0.36	6,193
19	area.1	0.00935	0.37	41,075
20	seat.1	0.00600	0.38	3,405
21	bud.2	0.00121	0.38	2,187
22	area.2	0.00222	0.38	2,994
23	area.3	0.02352	0.4	4,077
24	position.6	0.00919	0.41	802
25	place.13	0.01451	0.43	1,169
26	palm.1	0.00415	0.43	47,303
27	entity.1	0.01466	0.45	3,442
28	place.4	0.00951	0.46	16,059
29	area.5	0.00184	0.46	23,514
30	orange.2	0.00000	0.46	5,452
31	place.2	0.00152	0.46	46,083
32	thing.10	0.00302	0.46	2,768
33	leaf.1	0.00053	0.46	6,620
34	bud.1	0.01034	0.47	2,426
35	place.10	0.00034	0.47	1,472
36	wood.1	0.00498	0.48	33,953
37	growth.1	0.01587	0.49	1,506
38	sphere.1	0.00029	0.5	629

№	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
39	ash.1	0.00362	0.5	9,288
40	country.2	0.00775	0.51	21,151
41	seed.1	0.00177	0.51	2,290
42	seed.2	0.00172	0.51	3,471
43	place.12	0.00029	0.51	781
44	bean.2	0.00194	0.51	2,434
45	forest.2	0.00837	0.52	4,342
46	jam.1	0.00754	0.53	1,736
47	country.4	0.00633	0.53	11,953
48	home.1	0.01041	0.54	23,577
49	pea.1	0.00719	0.55	2,832
50	state.4	0.00056	0.55	8,389
51	violet.2	0.00983	0.56	8,303
52	apple.1	0.00025	0.56	12,158
53	plant.1	0.00018	0.56	3,756
54	sugar.1	0.00445	0.57	10,894
55	flower.2	0.00348	0.57	13,226
56	rose.1	0.00080	0.57	11,400
57	willow.1	0.00680	0.58	5,421
58	growth.2	0.00263	0.58	819
59	plant.2	0.00429	0.59	13,367
60	lumber.1	0.00419	0.59	914
61	sage.1	0.00179	0.59	2,629
62	<i>branch.3</i>	<i>0.00173</i>	<i>0.59</i>	<i>371</i>
63	fruit.1	0.00145	0.59	12,426
64	flower.1	0.00703	0.6	23,023
65	trunk.1	0.01189	0.61	7,897
66	source.3	0.01014	0.62	961
67	timber.2	0.00091	0.62	1,086
68	pepper.3	0.00015	0.62	2,782
69	weed.1	0.00244	0.63	4,968
70	rocket.1	0.00126	0.63	3,418
71	palm.3	0.00053	0.63	3,802
72	branch.2	0.00262	0.63	21,863
73	tree.1	0.00216	0.63	120,528
74	garden.2	0.00124	0.63	797
75	berry.1	0.00334	0.64	2,800
76	trunk.2	0.00093	0.64	4,793
77	moss.1	0.00009	0.64	2,936
78	pine.1	0.00118	0.64	5,523
79	place.15	0.00578	0.65	9,029
80	growth.4	0.00299	0.65	1,059
81	garden.1	0.00697	0.66	23,044
82	<i>decomposition.4</i>	<i>0.00386</i>	<i>0.66</i>	<i>467</i>
83	spice.1	0.00046	0.66	1,691
84	tree.2	0.00176	0.66	914
85	sage.3	0.00176	0.66	893
86	lemon.1	0.00562	0.67	2,544
87	herb.1	0.00069	0.67	1,431
88	forest.1	0.00014	0.67	41,290
89	herb.2	0.00030	0.67	3,751
90	daisy.1	0.00644	0.68	6,926

№	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
91	olfactory_property.1	0.00563	0.68	1,426
92	grape.1	0.00049	0.68	3,025
93	corn.1	0.00070	0.68	2,844
94	spice.2	0.00646	0.69	889
95	tobacco.1	0.00218	0.69	3,042
96	scent.2	0.00384	0.7	15,090
97	bean.1	0.00137	0.7	3,341
98	organism.1	0.00109	0.7	1,262
99	<i>spiciness.1</i>	0.00290	0.7	761
100	farm.1	0.00230	0.7	17,361
101	<i>fix.1</i>	0.00090	0.71	598
102	hayfield.1	0.00245	0.71	5,165
103	maple.1	0.00123	0.71	1,755
104	aroma.2	0.00253	0.71	27,648
105	turf.1	0.00057	0.71	911
106	<i>increase.3</i>	0.00176	0.71	411
107	landscape.1	0.00095	0.71	7,664
108	banana.2	0.00413	0.72	2,608
109	<i>park.2</i>	0.00093	0.72	590
110	<i>flower.3</i>	0.00348	0.72	339
111	petal.1	0.00076	0.72	3,391
112	pot.9	0.00096	0.72	1,299
113	violet.1	0.00324	0.73	917
114	strawberry.1	0.00032	0.73	3,759
115	ash.2	0.00666	0.74	1,381
116	sweet.3	0.00194	0.74	1,344
117	<i>sage.2</i>	0.00145	0.74	673
118	grass.1	0.00703	0.75	32,330
119	<i>planting.3</i>	0.00330	0.75	556
120	perfume.2	0.00055	0.75	2,094
121	<i>nectar.1</i>	0.00472	0.75	712
122	orange.1	0.00065	0.75	2,945
123	<i>growth.7</i>	0.00064	0.76	520
124	<i>pear.1</i>	0.00188	0.76	684
125	lawn.1	0.00112	0.76	11,972
126	coffee.1	0.00161	0.76	76,382
127	hay.1	0.00498	0.76	3,974
128	<i>rose.3</i>	0.00116	0.77	660
129	blackberry.1	0.01038	0.78	1,669
130	cabbage.1	0.00107	0.78	1,062
131	<i>fig.2</i>	0.00062	0.78	458
132	<i>fruit.3</i>	0.00178	0.78	385
133	<i>bean.3</i>	0.00016	0.78	418
134	vegetable.1	0.00301	0.78	6,058
135	tomato.1	0.00322	0.79	3,390
136	pine.2	0.00850	0.79	1,107
137	pasture.1	0.00441	0.8	2,519
138	<i>root.8</i>	0.00505	0.8	541
139	<i>timber.3</i>	0.00127	0.81	516
140	corn.3	0.00817	0.81	1,020
141	nation.2	0.00342	0.82	1,262
142	shrub.1	0.00419	0.82	2,028

Nº	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
143	greenhouse.1	0.00094	0.82	1,235
144	blight.1	0.00277	0.82	525
145	lemon.4	0.00067	0.83	515
146	leaf.2	0.00116	0.83	390
147	gamboge.2	0.01266	0.84	282
148	elm.1	0.00335	0.84	831
149	green.6	0.00264	0.85	723
150	garden.3	0.00298	0.85	5,285
151	turf.2	0.00547	0.85	563
152	planting.1	0.00044	0.85	237
153	monstrosity.2	0.00008	0.85	648
154	landscape.2	0.00157	0.86	521
155	greens.1	0.00195	0.86	469
156	jamming.1	0.00089	0.86	202
157	ancestry.2	0.00002	0.86	453
158	vitamin.1	0.00238	0.86	1,192
159	luggage_compartment.1	0.00079	0.86	4,380
160	myrtle.1	0.00077	0.86	1,090
161	salad.1	0.00453	0.87	5,088
162	torso.1	0.00256	0.87	386
163	pepper.4	0.00935	0.88	550
164	putrefaction.1	0.00569	0.88	432
165	yield.3	0.00139	0.89	276
166	proboscis.2	0.00300	0.89	358
167	freak.1	0.00211	0.89	688
168	coconut.1	0.00338	0.89	961
169	berry.2	0.01017	0.9	339
170	ancestor.1	0.00091	0.91	265
171	thing.11	0.00309	0.91	1,884
172	landscape.4	0.00114	0.91	229
173	capsicum.1	0.00529	0.92	267
174	plant.4	0.00186	0.92	171
175	poppy.1	0.00967	0.93	311
176	crush.2	0.00423	0.93	227
177	maple.2	0.00265	0.93	268
178	bundle.2	0.00001	0.93	934
179	alga.1	0.00591	0.94	391
180	corn.2	0.00209	0.94	308
181	carbohydrate.1	0.00529	0.95	312
182	orange.3	0.00045	0.95	217
183	melon.1	0.00554	0.95	918
184	banana.1	0.00996	0.96	226
185	lineage.1	0.00005	0.96	198
186	tulip.1	0.00203	0.97	811
187	farming.1	0.00098	0.97	295
188	turf.3	0.00595	0.97	213
189	beech.1	0.00945	0.98	226
190	root.3	0.00984	0.99	144
191	coffee.2	0.00292	0.99	969
192	shrubbery.2	0.00486	1	580
193	semen.1	0.01825	1.02	1,253
194	gelatin.2	0.00267	1.02	306

№	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
195	<i>fig.4</i>	0.00383	1.02	294
196	<i>coconut.2</i>	0.03818	1.06	230
197	<i>wood.8</i>	0.00231	1.06	131
198	<i>jelly.2</i>	0.02093	1.09	160
199	<i>apple.2</i>	0.01084	1.1	228
200	<i>honeysuckle.1</i>	0.00231	1.1	681
201	<i>wallflower.3</i>	0.01249	1.11	164
202	<i>lemon.3</i>	0.00806	1.12	182
203	<i>dogwood.1</i>	0.01836	1.14	199
204	<i>lilac.1</i>	0.02728	1.16	351
205	<i>avocado.1</i>	0.01061	1.18	433
206	<i>branch.5</i>	0.00902	1.18	106
207	<i>shrubbery.1</i>	0.01087	1.2	288
208	<i>agribusiness.1</i>	0.00113	1.2	143
209	<i>coconut.3</i>	0.00137	1.2	165
210	<i>oleander.1</i>	0.01293	1.21	142
211	<i>peony.1</i>	0.00497	1.22	166
212	<i>verbena.1</i>	0.00160	1.22	208
213	<i>landscape.3</i>	0.01531	1.23	128
214	<i>pea.3</i>	0.00981	1.24	92
215	<i>space.7</i>	0.01264	1.25	76
216	<i>dessert.1</i>	0.02932	1.28	89
217	<i>eggplant.1</i>	0.00079	1.28	158
218	<i>daffodil.1</i>	0.01914	1.3	473
219	<i>outgrowth.1</i>	0.00231	1.31	79
220	<i>radish.1</i>	0.00589	1.31	117
221	<i>pepper.1</i>	0.00100	1.31	84
222	<i>growth.6</i>	0.00608	1.32	77
223	<i>jelly.3</i>	0.01469	1.33	78
224	<i>timbre.1</i>	0.01146	1.35	70
225	<i>arm.2</i>	0.00377	1.35	64
226	<i>blight.2</i>	0.00008	1.35	76
227	<i>chrysanthemum.1</i>	0.01795	1.37	129
228	<i>care.1</i>	0.00357	1.37	64
229	<i>hyacinth.2</i>	0.00133	1.37	115
230	<i>root.4</i>	0.03485	1.41	64
231	<i>pieplant.1</i>	0.00092	1.41	103
232	<i>rocket.2</i>	0.01187	1.42	59
233	<i>attic.3</i>	0.01779	1.44	76
234	<i>tobacco.2</i>	0.00678	1.44	59
235	<i>plowing.1</i>	0.00031	1.44	61
236	<i>citron.1</i>	0.01800	1.46	62
237	<i>wallflower.1</i>	0.02070	1.48	53
238	<i>eatage.1</i>	0.03531	1.52	57
239	<i>boodle.1</i>	0.01772	1.54	51
240	<i>myrtle.2</i>	0.00199	1.54	47
241	<i>rocket.4</i>	0.01160	1.55	42
242	<i>skyrocket.2</i>	0.01000	1.56	41
243	<i>chocolate.3</i>	0.00251	1.56	45
244	<i>seeded_player.1</i>	0.02789	1.59	43
245	<i>sweet.4</i>	0.07324	1.66	33
246	<i>grape.2</i>	0.01409	1.68	33

№	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
247	<i>weed.2</i>	0.02553	1.7	31
248	<i>leaf.3</i>	0.01831	1.72	30
249	<i>solution.4</i>	0.01937	1.74	29
250	<i>planting.2</i>	0.01004	1.75	29
251	<i>coffee_bean.1</i>	0.00858	1.76	28
252	<i>palm.2</i>	0.02104	1.78	26
253	<i>organism.2</i>	0.04103	1.82	24
254	<i>elm.2</i>	0.01005	1.83	35
255	<i>pea.2</i>	0.01396	1.85	23
256	<i>orange.4</i>	0.03320	1.88	22
257	<i>pear.2</i>	0.00173	1.88	22
258	<i>wood.5</i>	0.01135	1.89	21
259	<i>eggplant.2</i>	0.08884	1.98	19
260	<i>green.4</i>	0.01331	1.99	17
261	<i>pod.2</i>	0.01109	2.01	17
262	<i>hyacinth.1</i>	0.03751	2.04	16
263	<i>tomato.2</i>	0.08484	2.13	13
264	<i>larkspur.1</i>	0.05837	2.19	12
265	<i>thing.12</i>	0.01829	2.2	11
266	<i>blush_wine.1</i>	0.00452	2.21	11
267	<i>foliation.3</i>	0.00168	2.21	11
268	<i>vegetable.2</i>	0.04595	2.26	10
269	<i>wood.3</i>	0.00498	2.26	10
270	<i>emergence.1</i>	0.04545	2.31	9
271	<i>tree.3</i>	0.06166	2.37	8
272	<i>ash.3</i>	0.00143	2.37	8
273	<i>blackberry.2</i>	0.00540	2.38	8
274	<i>wood.4</i>	0.06336	2.44	7
275	<i>chrysanthemum.2</i>	0.00539	2.44	7
276	<i>green.3</i>	0.00479	2.45	7
277	<i>lemon.5</i>	0.00024	2.45	7
278	<i>bunk.4</i>	0.06487	2.51	6
279	<i>figure.1</i>	0.00205	2.52	6
280	<i>cabbage.3</i>	0.00168	2.52	6
281	<i>melon.2</i>	0.00098	2.52	6
282	<i>plaza.1</i>	0.08801	2.61	5
283	<i>corn.7</i>	0.11570	2.72	4
284	<i>grapeshot.1</i>	0.00146	2.72	4
285	<i>woodwind.1</i>	0.14800	2.87	3
286	<i>wood.6</i>	0.00012	2.87	3
287	<i>supergrass.1</i>	0.00062	2.87	3
288	<i>ambrosia.4</i>	0.00041	2.87	3
289	<i>decoration.2</i>	0.20650	3.08	2
290	<i>nectar.2</i>	0.00020	3.08	2
291	<i>grass.2</i>	0.34780	3.43	1
292	<i>corn_whiskey.1</i>	0.00002	3.43	1
293	<i>etymon.1</i>	0.00001	3.43	1
294	<i>strawberry.3</i>	0.00000	3.43	1
295	<i>plant.3</i>	0.00001	3.43	1
296	<i>rocket.3</i>	0.00002	3.43	1
297	<i>department_of_agriculture.1</i>	0.00001	3.43	1
298	<i>willow.2</i>	0.00001	3.43	1

Nº	Synset	Abstraction	Cumulative	Count
299	<i>radish_plant.1</i>	<i>0.00006</i>	<i>3.43</i>	<i>1</i>
300	<i>dogwood.2</i>	<i>0.00001</i>	<i>3.43</i>	<i>1</i>
301	<i>avocado.2</i>	<i>0.00000</i>	<i>3.43</i>	<i>1</i>

C.4 *The BookCorpus Subset*

The collection of sentences from the BookCorpus that used the aforementioned target nouns can be found at <https://github.com/jesper-sk/msc-thesis-bookcorpus-synset-sentences>.